

MA in International Relations
University of Pécs
Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
Department of Political Science and International Studies

GEPOLITICS AND DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA

Author
Samat Kozhobaev

MA thesis written under the supervision of
Dr. Péter Kacziba

2023
Pécs, Hungary

Contents

GENERAL INTRODUCTION.....	4
1 CHAPTER: REGIONAL PERSPECTIVES.....	8
1.1. Iran.....	8
1.1.1. <i>Turan.....</i>	8
1.1.2. <i>Geopolitics.....</i>	9
1.1.3. <i>Development.....</i>	10
1.2. Turkey.....	11
1.2.1. <i>Pan-Turkism.....</i>	11
1.2.2. <i>Geopolitics.....</i>	12
1.2.3. <i>Development.....</i>	13
1.3. Russia.....	14
1.3.1. <i>Neo-Eurasianism.....</i>	14
1.3.2. <i>Geopolitics.....</i>	15
1.3.3. <i>Development.....</i>	16
1.4. China.....	18
1.4.1. <i>The New Silk Road (BRI).....</i>	18
1.4.2. <i>Geopolitics.....</i>	18
1.4.3. <i>Development.....</i>	19
2 CHAPTER: THEORETICAL ANALYSIS.....	21
2.1 Geopolitics.....	22
2.1.1 <i>Military intervention.....</i>	23
2.1.2 <i>International laws, agreements and rules.....</i>	25
2.1.3 <i>Aid.....</i>	28
2.1.4 <i>Trade.....</i>	31
2.2 Development.....	33
2.2.1 <i>Conflict trap.....</i>	36
2.2.2 <i>Landlocked with bad neighbors.....</i>	39
2.2.3 <i>Natural resource trap.....</i>	40
2.2.4 <i>Bad governance in a small country.....</i>	42
3 CHAPTER: CASE STUDIES.....	46
3.1 Conflict in Tajikistan.....	47
3.2 Double-landlocked Uzbekistan.....	51
3.3 Resource curse of Turkmenistan.....	57
3.4 Bad governance in Kyrgyzstan.....	62
4 THESIS CONCLUSION.....	68
5 References.....	71

TABLE OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1: Central Asia</i>	3
<i>Figure 2: Remittances as % of GDP</i>	17
<i>Figure 3: Military expenditure of Security Council members, Iran, India and Turkey in 2021</i>	24
<i>Figure 4: Official Development Assistance from OECD received as % of GNI</i>	29
<i>Figure 5: GDP and Democracy normality of the world and abnormality in LLDCs</i>	35
<i>Figure 6: Democracy and Peace</i>	38
<i>Figure 7: Resource rents as a % of GDP</i>	41
<i>Figure 8: GDP growth rate (annual %)</i>	44
<i>Figure 9: Good Governance Ranking in CA</i>	45
<i>Figure 10: GDP and Debt of Kyrgyzstan (current US\$)</i>	64

Figure 1: Central Asia

Source: (Geographic Guide), <https://www.geographicguide.com/asia/maps/central-asia.htm>, retrieved February 2, 2023.

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

It is hard to think of a better geopolitical example than Central Asia (CA). The region's three main neighbors are all rivals of the West – Iran, Russia and China. Located in the heart of the Eurasian continent, CA has been broadly considered to be a part of the Russian sphere of influence. On the other hand, economic expansion of China has also influenced the geopolitics and development of the region. Turkey does not share border with the region and positions itself as an ally of the West, however, pursues its own far-reaching goals and counts as a regional power as well. At this point, it is necessary to clarify the definition of the West used in this thesis. The West is a collective definition of European Union, the United Kingdom and the USA and, in a few cases, the definition will imply the NATO. Presumably, since the fall of the Soviet Union, according to the general rules of geopolitics, the winning side – the West – should have assertively established and solidified its presence in the regions where the losing side – Russia – has considerably weakened its presence. Contrary to this assumption, the West has largely retreated from the geopolitical game in CA despite the fact that there were some successful cases of cooperation.¹ From bad to worse, the withdrawal of the US troops from Afghanistan in 2021 produced a ripple effect of panic across CA.² Four regional powers interact with each other in the region and they find as many points of common interest as there are potential sources of conflict.

When it comes to the concept of development, CA also conceals many paradoxes and discrepancies. During the Soviet Era, the region had been developed by the Russians and largely disconnected from the rest of the world, including the West. Social development comprising of education, healthcare, infrastructure and transportation was boosted and commanded from Moscow. Industrialization was also in the plans of Moscow and the process was impressive especially due to transferring industrial enterprises from the frontline to CA during the Second World War (Hiro, 2011, p. 56). A post-war development had also reshaped the region, especially in the sector of agriculture, leading to the direst man-made environmental catastrophe in the human history – the Aral Sea desiccation. This catastrophe is a great example for the importance of unsustainable development, as in this case the wellbeing of the future generations has been sacrificed for the economic development of a

¹ Umarov, Temur (April 6, 2021): Is There a Place for a U.S. Military Base in Central Asia? Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, <https://carnegiemoscow.org/commentary/84685>, retrieved January 6, 2023.

² Stepansky, Joseph (August 23, 2021): US military presence in Central Asia unlikely amid Taliban rise. Al Jazeera, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/8/23/us-military-presence-in-central-asia-unlikely-amid-taliban-rise>, retrieved November 6, 2022.

present generation at that time. The whole process of development had a top-down vector in the Soviet Union and a supply chain of production was built in isolation from the rest of the world. As a result, after the collapse of the Soviet Union, the development process has halted, and CA inherited transportation, logistics and supply network which all led to Russia limiting the region of trade diversification. Post-Soviet CA went through hard times of transition period, which is featured by inflation, unemployment and economic stagnation. The traces of 'isolated' development of the region still can be seen in extreme dependency on Moscow in security and economic donations. In contrast, high general literacy level was achieved and education received heavy investment during socialism and can be regarded as the most positive aspect of the Soviet period (Aslund, 2007, p. 14).

The short overview indicated that geopolitics impacts development. The question is how? The question is short, yet complex and there is no unanimity among scholars. For instance, the perspective of the world-system by Immanuel Wallerstein emphasizes the neocolonialist spirit of modern capitalism, which is designed for exploitation by the capitalist powers. Wallerstein (2006, pp. 54) wrote:

“It has been able to achieve an absolutely extraordinary expansion of technology and wealth, but it has been able to do this only at the cost of an ever increasing polarization of the world-system between an upper 20 percent and a bottom 80 percent – a polarization that has been at one and the same time economic, political, social and cultural.”

Human history is abundant with instances when geopolitical confrontation between powers has been devastating for poor countries. The Age of Imperialism left the former colonies impoverished in Asia and Africa which were later labeled as the Third World countries. On the other hand, Walt Whitman Rostow (1959, pp. 6) generalized that “Without the affront to human and national dignity caused by the intrusion of more advanced powers, the rate of modernization of traditional societies over the past century-and-a-half would have been much slower than, in fact, it has been.”

How can two respected scholars arrive to opposing conclusions on the same topic? Therefore, it is a central intellectual challenge for this study to find out if geopolitics can be constructive and generate positive spillover effect that will stimulate development across the contested regions and states. So, the task of this thesis is difficult and, oftentimes, controversial. But in the case of solid findings, this thesis may add a fundamental contribution to developmental studies that should drift away from a current mainstream perspective of incompatibility between geopolitics and development.

Brief description of chapters

The first chapter introduces CA through different perspectives. “Central Asia” is an easily comprehensible definition fitting a Western mindset. Since Westerners have a very straightforward approach in interacting with the environment and, quite rationally, they refer to the spatial approximate center of Eurasian continent as Central Asia. The term doesn’t convey a complex meaning but rather adheres to a simplified geographical definition and largely projects Western realist geostrategic view. The five countries of CA, despite sharing common modern history, are very different, and they are perceived differently by the regional powers. *The chapter introduces four perspectives which reveal diverse dimensions and contribute to better understanding of the region.* Those four perspectives are Iranian, Turkish, Russian and Chinese. The alternative perspectives are not limited to geography but often originate from historical, ethnic, political, cultural and economic dimensions.

Second chapter essentially attempts to grasp a theoretical and practical evolution of the concepts of geopolitics and development. The post-war world order has openly condemned and abolished the territorial conquest model of geopolitics. Former colonies and peripheries have become sovereign states, and former empires now have to find new ways of projecting their power externally. The former empires, though, still operate from an imperial mindset (Kaplan, 2018, pp. 18-19). The definition of development has also started narrowly as the economic growth. Clearly, economic approach to development is not holistic, therefore, the definition evolved to additionally imply democracy, human rights, security.

The chapter continues with the analysis of Paul Collier, the British economist and the University of Oxford alma mater. He published a book named “The Bottom Billion” in 2007. The book categorizes developing countries into four traps: Conflict, Natural resources, Landlocked with bad neighbors, Bad governance in a small country. These traps have been preventing the countries from developing. Collier’s analysis extends further to also present four “instruments” that could help these countries break free of the traps: Aid, Military intervention, Laws and Trade. Yet, there are two gaps in the analysis of Collier. First, he concentrated on analyzing the developing countries in Sub-Saharan Africa and ignored Central Asian countries. Second, the book analysis revolves around the role of the West and ignores the contribution of other actors. *The second chapter analyzes the evolution of geopolitics and development and updates it with examples according to Collier’s classification.*

Third chapter studies four cases in CA according to Collier's analysis. Each of the Collier's traps have a vivid case in the region. All four cases substantially demonstrate what regional powers do, and how their actions alleviate or escalate problems in the region. The analysis is multidimensional since there are four regional powers, Western interference, non-state actors, unique regional political culture and geography involved. *Hence, the third chapter culminates by addressing the research question about the impact of geopolitics on development in Central Asia.*

Research methodology

The research methodology used in this thesis is a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses. In addition to studying scholarly and journalistic publications in order to grasp the trends, attitudes and patterns, the research engages in exploration of the historical background to identify alternative perspectives. Learning alternative perspectives allows the reader to broaden his outlook and get acquainted with the character of the region. Central Asia is understudied and, in many cases, overlooked. Some Western academic works devoted to the region treat it as an object rather than a subject. For example, Peter Hopkirk (1990) wrote about the confrontation of the British Empire and Tsarist Russia in Central Asia in the 1800's in his book "The Great Game: On Secret Service in High Asia". Central Asia and Afghanistan are depicted as a contested territory and a buffer zone between the two empires. Tom Miller (2017) projects the Chinese vision of the region as a valuable source of hydrocarbons and the New Silk Road. The primary goal of the thesis is to analyze the impact of geopolitics on development in CA. The research method is an expansion of the analysis in the book of Paul Collier – "The Bottom Billion".

Quantitative analysis plays a complementary function to the main qualitative part of the research. Quantitative data is often presented in visuals to solidify and complement the ideas of the author. The level of quantitative calculations is intermediate which is sufficient to see the patterns and support assumptions and ideas. Statistical data is presented where it is convenient to demonstrate an idea in numbers and tables.

The data in the research is secondary with availability on the internet. The main categories are academic publications, journal articles, governmental press release articles, NGO reports, mainstream and documentary films. Besides qualitative data, quantitative data has also been presented in the thesis. Such data is available on the websites of UN organizations, NGOs and governmental organizations. The data has been edited to provide a deeper understanding for the reader. The nature of the thesis doesn't require collection of primary data but requires to study numerous different works related to the topic.

1 CHAPTER: REGIONAL PERSPECTIVES

At different periods in history, the region has been defined as a habitat of nomadic tribes, a transit route, a buffer zone, a sphere of influence, a space for expansion etc. Neighboring regional powers such as Russia, China and Iran have maintained dominant roles in relations with CA. Turkic ethnicity of Turkey and its geopolitical aspirations also link it with the region. The exclusion of India and Pakistan from the list is based on such rationality that the interactions between CA and these regional players are not significant. Obviously, Pakistan and India attempt to strengthen ties with CA but those bilateral and multilateral meetings have rarely been productive. As the Tajik president, Emomali Rahmon, criticized these C5+ format multilateral meetings with different powers as empty talks noting India and Pakistan among them.³ It is sufficient to study the history of CA from the perspective of the four regional powers.

Every political entity has a model of the world with different identities and labels. Such a model helps to simplify the structure of the international system and differentiate “us” from “them”. The dichotomy of “us” and “them” is infected with an assumption that “they” are automatically inferior to “us”. Although such viewpoint is not nurturing cooperation on equal terms, it had prevailed especially in the West (Huntington, 1996, pp. 58-59).

The alternative concepts of CA are proposed in the perspectives of Iran, Turkey, Russia and China. These states have been growing more assertive in the region and have often demonstrated mutual intentions to cooperate. They have been very skillful in learning how to play by local rules. “East is a delicate matter” – an iconic phrase of Sukhov, a Red Army soldier, from a legendary Soviet movie eloquently transcends the essence of Central Asia (Motyl, 1970). Therefore, knowledge of different perspectives builds deeper understanding of the region and brings this research closer to answer how geopolitics impact development in Central Asia.

1.1. Iran

1.1.1. Turan

The Islamic Republic of Iran is the successor state of former Persia. In ancient times, Persia founded big cities in the arable basins of the rivers Syr Darya and Amu Darya – Samarkand, Tashkent, Bukhara, Khwarazm, Mari, Khujand etc. (Golden, 2011, pp. 18-20). Nowadays, the cities are located in Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Tajikistan. Mountainous parts of

³ Eurasianet (October 17, 2022): Was Tajik leader’s rant at Putin defiance or a plea for greater dependence? Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/was-tajik-leaders-rant-at-putin-defiance-or-a-plea-for-greater-dependence>, retrieved January 1, 2023.

Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and the vast arid steppes of Kazakhstan were not of great importance for Persia, moreover, the nomadic, predominantly Turkic tribes inhabited those lands. Military superiority of the nomads was another factor why Persia rarely plotted expansion to the northern territories. Nomadic ‘barbarian’ civilization in CA was perceived as an antipode of the Persian civilization. This perspective of contrasts resulted in the concept of Turan (the land of Turs) as the opposite of Iran (the land of Aryans). Initially, ancient Persia distinguished Persian tribes between Iran and Turan, where the latter represented the fierce and evil nomadic Persian people that inhabited the lands beyond Amu Darya, which is practically Central Asia (Ibid, p. 4). However, later, a famous ancient Persian poet, Firdausi, used this term to denote the “lands inhabited by Turkic speaking tribes” in his biased anti-Arab and anti-Turk book named *Shahnama* “Book of Kings” (Diakonoff, 1999, pp. 99-100). Although Turan is an Ancient Persian term, nonetheless, it has found many sympathizers in Turkey. The most prominent Turkic state has never given up its pursuit of greatness and often plays with this term. Even Hungary had been playing with this concept in its search for self-identity and response to Pan-German and Pan-Slavic movements in the 19th century (Gökhun Dayioğlu, 2022, p. 231). Idealized fusion of geography, history, culture and gone golden age composed the concept for Hungarians in the era of nationalism. Turan was a Hungarian utopia in the times when people felt isolated, insecure and lonely on the European continent.

1.1.2. Geopolitics

Iran borders with only Turkmenistan from the Central Asian states, but it has ethnic and cultural ties with Tajikistan. The modern-day Turkmenistan de jure was under Persia when Russian Empire annexed it by forcing Persia to sign the Treaty of Akhal in 1881 (Golden, 2011, p. 23).⁴ Due to the Western sanctions and the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Iran sees a geopolitical opportunity in CA. A security weakening geopolitical episode in the relations of Iran and Tajikistan took place in the spring 2022, when the opening of the Iranian drone factory was officially inaugurated in Tajikistan.⁵ Iran-Tajik relations are very complex. Iran is the core state of Shia Muslims and Tajikistan is predominantly Sunni. But Tajikistan has Shia Muslims in the eastern part of the country – Gorno-Badakhshan Autonomous Region (GBAO, author note: the word ‘region’ translates to Russian as

⁴ Meteojournal (May 27, 2021): Istorija formirovaniya granicy Turkmenskoj SSR. Meteojournal, <https://meteojournal.ru/istoriya-formirovaniya-granicy-turkmenskoj-ssr/>, retrieved January 14, 2023.

⁵ Kaleji, Vali (June 14, 2022): Iran Opens Ababil-2 Drone Factory in Tajikistan: Reasons and Implications. The Jamestown Foundation publication: Eurasia Daily Monitor, <https://jamestown.org/program/iran-opens-ababil-2-drone-factory-in-tajikistan-reasons-and-implications/>, retrieved January 27, 2023.

область, English transliteration – oblast’). They are collectively known as Pamiri people and their struggle for real autonomy and political rights against Dushanbe continues since the collapse of the Soviet Union. GBAO occupies nearly half of the territory of Tajikistan but comprises less than 3% of the population (Parshin, 2016, p. 85). Although autonomous status of the region is recognized in the Constitution of Tajikistan, in practice, Dushanbe tries to suppress and control the region. This internal conflict in Tajikistan produces dilemma for Iran as it is forced to choose between cooperation with ethnically related but Sunni central government or support religiously related but oppressed Shia minority.⁶ Such a relationship only consolidates the authoritarian regime of Tajikistan by actually militarizing the central government. A strong aspect of power securitization is a part of political culture in CA. Local leaders have perfected their skills in consolidating their rule with the assistance of the powers, whereas those powers play peekaboo at their convenience. Similarly, Iran turns blind eye on the oppression of the Shia minority because Tajikistan is a valuable partner in the confrontation of Islamist threat from Afghanistan. Besides, its geopolitical strategy in Tajikistan seems to align with the strategies of two other powers – Russia and China – as they collectively attempt to enhance security in the region (Yuldasheva, 2017, pp. 37-38).

1.1.3. Development

Iran doesn't have significant investment capabilities; however, it has invested in a number of development projects in Tajikistan. Some of the projects were extremely critical like Anzob tunnel connecting Dushanbe and Khujand (Foltz, 2019, p. 121). The construction of the tunnel in 2015 was essential since a trip between two major cities had to loop through Uzbekistan. For the most part of the winter season, two cities were practically cut off from each other, which underscores the harsh geographic reality of Tajikistan. Some unfinished projects from the Soviet period have been completed with Iranian investments such as Sangtuda-2 hydroelectric power plant.⁷ The confrontation with the West pushes Iran to consider alternatives for cooperation. The most obvious alternative is the Chinese Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). China cooperates with Pakistan and operates Gwadar port – this cooperation bypasses CA and prevents it from fully benefiting in the BRI. Iranian ports, especially Chabahar Port, are considered as an alternative; in this case, Iran-China

⁶ Clark, Brenton (April 10, 2022): Persian games: Iran's strategic foothold in Tajikistan. openDemocracy, <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/odr/persian-games-irans-strategic-foothold-in-tajikistan/>, retrieved January 2, 2023.

⁷ Ibid

cooperation will definitely lead to convergence of CA with global trade.⁸ The Aga Khan Development Network (AKDN) is founded by His Highness the Aga Khan, the 49th hereditary Imam (Spiritual Leader) of the Shia Imami Ismaili Muslims.⁹ AKDN is strongly dedicated to developing rural communities by building schools and hospitals, providing microfinance and small business opportunities. The AKDN and Iran operate in Tajikistan independently and pursue different goals. The Network features a Westernized approach, notably, the founder and chairman bears the official title His Highness granted by the Queen Elizabeth II (Parshin, 2016, p. 87). According to some estimates, the economy of GBAO receives more assistance from AKDN than from Dushanbe (Grogan, 2021, p. 5). Contrastingly, the Tajik government conducts crackdowns in GBAO seeing AKDN related institutions as a threat.¹⁰ In conclusion, unlike Iran-the West animosity, Iran-the East relations are more promising, less thorny yet tricky, especially in CA.

1.2. Turkey

1.2.1. Pan-Turkism

Central Asia is ethnically dominated by Turkic people, but the strongest Turkic state – Turkey – is spatially separated from the region. The rulers of the Ottoman Empire witnessing the disintegration of their empire searched for a concept of consolidation. Three options were Pan-Ottomanism, Pan-Turkism/Pan-Turanism and Pan-Islamism (Hiro, 2011, p. 65). Pan-Ottomanism was crossed out as the empire kept crumbling. Kemal Ataturk, the leader of the successor state – Turkey – sympathized consolidation around the national identity with Pan-Turkism rather than around religious identity with Pan-Islamism. His sympathy for national identity might have started to form in his early life in Thessaloniki where he witnessed Greek nationalism and Westernization while serving as a soldier of the decaying Ottoman Empire. In other words, Ataturk's reactive nationalism was a driving force behind Turkey's consolidation and modernization (Rostow, 1959, p. 6). Even nowadays Pan-Turkism is used interchangeably with Pan-Ottomanism because both of them originate in the post-empire power, but as explained earlier, each conveys a different vision. Yet, Robert Kaplan (2018, pp. 19-20) interprets the regional policy of Turkey under Recep Tayyip Erdogan as neo-Ottomanism. The most prominent Pan-Turkism proponent in Tsarist Russia was a Tatar

⁸ Aliasgary, Soroush – Ekstrom, Marin (October 21, 2021): Chabahar Port and Iran's Strategic Balancing with China and India. The Diplomat, <https://thediplomat.com/2021/10/chabahar-port-and-irans-strategic-balancing-with-china-and-india/>, retrieved January 27, 2023.

⁹ The Aga Khan Development Network (n.d.): FAQ. AKDN, <https://the.akdn/en/how-we-work/our-approach/frequently-asked-questions>, retrieved January 27, 2023.

¹⁰ Eurasianet (July 22, 2022): Tajikistan puts the squeeze on Aga Khan-linked entities. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/tajikistan-puts-the-squeeze-on-aga-khan-linked-entities>, retrieved January 29, 2023.

intellectual from Crimea – Ismail Gasprinski. He advocated for the unity of Muslim Turkic people of the Russian Empire, practically, mixing the concepts of nation and religion (Feneis, 1992, p. 21). To his defense, it should be noted that Gasprinski promoted modernization and reforms in education of Muslim Turkic people in the Russian Empire (Golden, 2011, pp. 130-131). After the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Turkey's aspirations for hegemony in CA under the umbrella of Pan-Turkism didn't fully materialize since the unification propensity of the region is extremely weak (Feneis, 1992, p. 2). Therefore, instead of building an instant Pan-Turkic union in Central Asia, Turkey has to implement a long-term strategy for integration with the region.

1.2.2. Geopolitics

Turkey is one of the most geopolitically motivated powers and its determination only strengthens as it becomes disillusioned with the goal to join the EU. Kemalist state with the Western orientation is a figure of the past; Turkish society is now too complicated for that (Kaplan, 2018, p. 20). Its Eastern ambitions and chances were bolstered in 2022 as Azerbaijan regained Nagorno-Karabakh from Armenia with the help of Turkish military assistance and drones, which products of the Turkish arms industry showed effectiveness in Ukraine as well.¹¹ A peculiar comparison of Turkey-Azerbaijan and Iran-Tajikistan relations demonstrates that the Sunni-Shia schism in Islam can be conveniently muted in geopolitics. Kyrgyzstan used Turkish drones during the border conflict with Tajikistan in September 2022, but the interesting part is that Tajikistan had also planned to acquire Turkish drones. Yet it is not confirmed that Tajikistan succeeded since Turkey was under pressure by the secretary-general of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS).¹² Such a strong tendency for militarization is a part of Central Asian political culture. Turkish hydrocarbon dependency and the Uighur suppression in Xinjiang forces it to balance relations with China. Natural resources of Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan could diversify energy supplies to Turkey and excess could be streamed to European markets, but China has been investing heavily in the hydrocarbon industry of CA for its own consumption. Moreover, human rights violations of Uighurs, who are of Turkic ethnicity, in Xinjiang have infuriated nationalistically tuned politicians in Turkey, but lucrative BRI projects and Chinese investments are the benefits

¹¹ Donnellon-May, Genevieve (October 13, 2022): Turkey's Growing Influence in Central Asia. The Diplomat, <https://thediplomat.com/2022/10/turkeys-growing-influence-in-central-asia/>, retrieved October 15, 2022.

¹² Tastekin, Fehim (September 26, 2022): Are Turkish drones complicating disputes in Central Asia? Al-Monitor.com, <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/09/are-turkish-drones-complicating-disputes-central-asia>, retrieved January 28, 2023.

that Turkey can't afford to risk by hassling with China.¹³ Turkey has to play a geopolitical game in CA, yet it is motivated to do so betting on its own geostrategic position and ethnic ties with regional states.

1.2.3. Development

Turkey continues its strategy to establish itself as a unifying power around the idea of Pan-Turkism. Institutional representation of this concept is OTS. The organization envisages cooperation in politics, economics, education, transport, and tourism; overall, the official OTS website lists 19 Areas of Cooperation.¹⁴ Turkey doesn't have economic power of China or Russian regional ties nurtured for decades, but its image and influence may rise if it follows current development strategy. Turkish system of education proved superior to post-Soviet one in quality. For example, Kyrgyz "Sapat" (rebranded Turkish "Sebat") is a popular and prestigious educational institution, shaping positive image of Turkey. Ironically, the Turkish government has forced Kyrgyzstan to close the institution due to its links to Fethullah Gülen, who is one of the main suspects in the failed 2016 coup in Turkey, but the governments negotiated a deal by exerting more state control over the institution.¹⁵ Even isolationist Turkmenistan with strong Turkmenization policies hasn't closed Turkish schools as it has been doing with Russian, Uzbek and Kazakh schools (Bohr, 2016, pp. 43-44). Kazakh and Turkmen seaports at the Caspian Sea are integral for the Middle Corridor – Turkey's version of the new Silk Road. Turkey's Ministry of Foreign Affairs describes the project as Trans-Caspian East-West-Middle Corridor Initiative.¹⁶ Turkmenbashi seaport in Turkmenistan was modernized by a Turkish enterprise and inaugurated in 2018; Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway is the section on the western shore of the sea, and together these facilities and routes should bring the grand vision of the Middle Corridor to life.¹⁷ This grand connectivity project can also be considered as geopolitics. Turkey takes balanced approach in CA but its grand vision can harmoniously merge with that of China. However, despite

¹³ Tastekin, Fehim (January 5, 2023): Turkey spars with China over Uyghurs, but is it real? Al-Monitor.com, <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2023/01/turkey-spars-china-over-uyghurs-it-real>, retrieved January 29, 2023.

¹⁴ Organization of Turkic States (n.d.): Areas of Cooperation. OTS official website, <https://www.turkicstates.org/en/isbirligi-alanlari>, retrieved January 29, 2023.

¹⁵ Eurasianet (July 26, 2016): Kyrgyzstan: Antagonism Grows with Turkey Over Gülen Links. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/kyrgyzstan-antagonism-grows-turkey-over-gulen-links>, retrieved January 29, 2023.

¹⁶ Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Türkiye (n.d.): Türkiye's Multilateral Transportation Policy. MFA of the Republic of Türkiye official website, https://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkey_s-multilateral-transportation-policy.en.mfa, retrieved January 30, 2023.

¹⁷ Ibid.

overlap of its interests with the interests of other powers, Turkey claims it has no intention to compete but to cooperate in the region.¹⁸

1.3. Russia

1.3.1. Neo-Eurasianism

Central Asia had been under the Russian rule for over hundred years. During this period, the comprehension of the region had been shifting from Turkestan (predominantly under the Tsarist Russia) to Near Abroad (Yeltsin's Russia) and finally to Neo-Eurasianism currently. This term is not very popular but eloquently explains Russian historical and imperialistic motives (Kaplan, 2018, p. 25). Considerable Russian expansion into Central Asia started in the mid-19th century. The loss in the Crimean War to Ottoman Empire had been a humiliation, and the Russian Empire sought a geopolitical revanche. Therefore, Neo-Eurasianism embeds imperialistic geostrategy additionally loaded with ethnocentrism, expansionism, confrontation with the West and perception of Central Asia as a rightful extension of Russian influence. Huntington (1996) interprets the West as a unique civilization; Neo-Eurasianism applies the same principle for Russia. The father of this ideology is a Russian geopolitical thinker, Alexander Dugin. To some extent, Dugin is similar to Vladimir Putin as Ratzel was to Adolf Hitler. There is an absolute conviction that CA must integrate with Russia preferably in the form of Eurasian Union (Dugin, 2014, p. 65). The nature of Neo-Eurasianism ideology was embedded in the rhetoric of Putin when he claimed that the collapse of the Soviet Union was the greatest geopolitical catastrophe of the 20th century, especially for those ethnic Russians who suddenly found themselves outside Russia. The Sovietization was also acclaimed as a civilizing and modernizing process with stress on equality among nations, but Russian culture and language were dominant and prioritized for state-level promotion (Dickens, 1989, pp. 5-7). The power of Russian chauvinism was badly underestimated, but the stated reasons of the invasion of Ukraine have alerted Central Asian states, especially Kazakhstan since it has considerable ethnic Russian population. Kazakh president – Kassym-Jomart Tokayev – stated that Lugansk and Donetsk People's Republics are not recognized by Kazakhstan at the public meeting with Putin in St Petersburg in June 2022.¹⁹ It can be assumed that Putin could have invaded northern

¹⁸ Köstem, Seçkin (October 1, 2019): The Power of the Quiet? Turkey's Central Asia Strategy. Italian Institute for International Political Studies, <https://www.ispionline.it/en/publicazione/power-quiet-turkeys-central-asia-strategy-24069>, retrieved January 30, 2023.

¹⁹ Baunov, Peter (June 20, 2022): Face to face with Putin, Kazakhstan's president refuses to recognise Ukraine breakaway republics. bne IntelliNews, <https://intellinews.com/face-to-face-with-putin-kazakhstan-s-president-refuses-to-recognise-ukraine-breakaway-republics-248002/>, retrieved March 10, 2023.

Kazakhstan with the largest ethnic Russian population if it had a blitzkrieg in Ukraine. The reasons for invasion would have been same old protection of Russians from discrimination. Neo-Eurasianism can also be interpreted as a refurbished Soviet ideology defining the West as a quintessential rival and sacred dreams to regain post-Soviet territories including CA. Russia encapsulates its geopolitical ideal in Neo-Eurasianism but doesn't disguise chauvinistic notes.

1.3.2. Geopolitics

Russian self-identity as a great power hasn't vanished with the Soviet Union. It still considers former-Soviet states as its sphere of influence. Every institution founded by Russia, even formally economic institutions, has had a political foundation. For instance, the Eurasian Economic Union (EEU) makes economic sense for Kazakhstan and Belarus due to the Soviet infrastructure connectivity, but Armenia and Kyrgyzstan had to join due to their dependency on remittances and cheap energy from Russia.²⁰ Such exchange of economic benefits for political loyalty has nurtured clientelism in CA as a strong characteristic of the local political culture. Russia, witnessing successful geopolitical expansion of the West, has tried to copy. The NATO copy is the Collective Security Treaty of 1992, which is the founding document of Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) created in 2002.²¹ The members of this organization include Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia and Tajikistan. The CSTO has demonstrated its impotence recently when its member, Armenia, invoked the Article 4 of the treaty in September, 2022, in response to the allegedly Azerbaijani violation of a ceasefire agreement; the CSTO refrained from intervening militarily.²² The first enforcement of the Article 4 of the Treaty was in January, 2022, when Kazakhstan was caught in unrest.²³ The response was immediate and peacekeeping forces from Russia, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan entered Kazakhstan to stabilize the situation. This organization has a lot of friction and internal confrontation. Armenian citizens protested for withdrawal from the CSTO soon after Armenia was refused of the assistance when it desperately needed. Border disputes and clashes between two members – Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan – have escalated to open hostility on intergovernmental level. The CSTO military

²⁰ Wolczuk K., Dragneva, R., Wallace, J. (July 15, 2022): What is the Eurasian Economic Union? Chatham House, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2022/07/what-eurasian-economic-union>, retrieved January 30, 2023

²¹ Collective Security Treaty Organization (n.d.): From the Treaty to the Organization. CSTO, <https://en.odkb-csto.org/25years/>, retrieved January 23, 2023.

²² Mejlumyan, Ani (September 15, 2022): For Armenians, CSTO missing in action. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/for-armenians-csto-missing-in-action>, retrieved January 21, 2023.

²³ Kucera, Joshua (January 5, 2022): CSTO agrees to intervene in Kazakhstan unrest, <https://eurasianet.org/csto-agrees-to-intervene-in-kazakhstan-unrest>, retrieved January 21, 2023.

drills on the territory of Kyrgyzstan planned for October, 2022, were postponed by the Kyrgyz government and one of the stated reasons is that the tensions hadn't cooled down between two states.²⁴ Notably, Russia's largest military station is in Tajikistan – 201st Military base (former 201st Motorized Rifle Division) has an objective to secure border with Afghanistan, but its impact on regional geopolitics and Tajik politics has been integral throughout its long history.²⁵

Russian diasporas in CA are also exploited in Russian geopolitics. Quite often Moscow has used them as a reason to intervene, and this practice has a long history. Ukraine is not the first country to suffer from Russian aggression. Central Asian revolt of 1916 against conscription of local men for labor works at the European theater of war during the First World War can generally be defined as a genocide. Around 4,000 ethnic Russians were killed by the locals in the wave of violence but the suppression of the revolt and persecution of the fleeing by the Russian Army resulted in fatalities of around 200,000 Central Asians.²⁶ The conscription was only a spark to the revolt since there were a few other factors like distribution of the best arable lands to the new settlers and other discriminatory policies.²⁷ Thousands of Kazakh and Kyrgyz fled to Eastern Turkestan what is now Xinjiang. Interestingly, Vladimir Putin visited Kyrgyzstan on September 17, 2016 and actually attended the ceremony of wreath laying at the 1916 Revolt Memorial Center.²⁸ Prioritized position of Russians and Russian language in CA has always been a political leverage for Moscow, but it refrained from actively intervening to protect the local Russians in Turkmenistan in order to secure revenues generated by exporting Ashgabat's gas to Europe. Moscow has once again confirmed that it treats ethnic Russians as a trade-off for geopolitical gains.

1.3.3. Development

The main contribution of Russia to development in CA has been remittances from the labor migrants. Due to high unemployment and low wages in the region, many young people from the rural regions travel to Russia for low-skilled jobs in the construction and service sectors.

²⁴ Kovalev, Petr (October 13, 2022): Uchenija ODKB v Kirgizii perenesli na bolee pozdnij srok. TASS.RU, <https://tass.ru/mezhdunarodnaya-panorama/16044133>, retrieved January 21, 2023.

²⁵ GlobalSecurity.org (n.d.): Operational Group of Russian Forces in Tajikistan. GlobalSecurity.org, <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/russia/ogrv-tajikistan.htm>, retrieved February 24, 2023.

²⁶ Karpazli, Ertan (June 25, 2016): Kyrgyzstan still burying the past 100 years after Urkun. TRT World, <https://www.trtworld.com/magazine/kyrgyzstan-still-burying-the-past-100-years-after-urkun-1833>, retrieved November 23, 2022.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ The Kremlin (September 17, 2016): Wreath laying at memorials in Kyrgyzstan. The Kremlin official website, <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/52906>, retrieved February 20, 2023.

The number of migrants from CA is in millions and the remittances represent around 30% of GDP for Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, that is billions of US\$ sent back to the countries annually. The situation with labor migration has worsened due to the COVID-19 and the war in Ukraine. Such dependency on remittances is exploited by Russia as a political tool.

Figure 2: Remittances as % of GDP

Source: own editing, data source: (The World Bank), Personal remittances, received (% of GDP) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.TRF.PWKR.DT.GD.ZS>, retrieved February 11, 2023.

Soviet infrastructure and ties that function to these days allows Russia to exert political leverage. Gas and oil of CA had been exported predominantly via Russian pipelines until foreign investors from the West and China flooded in the region. Especially Turkmen gas is pumped to China since 2009 leaving Moscow as a secondary partner in export options. Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan depend on the subsidized fuel and gas from Moscow, which is essential for their economies. Moscow's geopolitical dream to build a new empire in the form of the EEU has also increased development assistance to CA. Russian-Kyrgyz Development Fund founded in 2014 finances businesses in agriculture, manufacturing, tourism and other sectors.²⁹ But extreme kleptocracy in the post-Soviet states and Russia inhibits development and integration of Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan with the EEU. However, kleptocracy is not an accidental byproduct of the post-Soviet autocratic governance but a deliberately nurtured environment in order to ease illegal enrichment.

²⁹ Russian-Kyrgyz Development Fund (July 19, 2022): Informacziya o vydannyh kreditah na 01.12.2022. Russian-Kyrgyz Development Fund official website, <https://www.rkdf.org/vidannie-kreditu/>, retrieved January 31, 2023.

1.4. China

1.4.1. The New Silk Road (BRI)

The Silk Road trade routes lay from China to Europe through Central Asia. It flourished until the discovery of sea routes. Stagnation and decline of the Silk Road practically turned CA into backwaters of the world politics. But currently China is on the rise, and its economic might needs a room for expansion and soaring internal wealth has already been spilling over its borders. In order to gauge and guide this spill over, President Xi Jinping announced his grand initiative – the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). This initiative can be roughly divided into two parts – Silk Road Economic Belt and Maritime Silk Road. Actually, Xi announced each part separately at two different events. He first mentioned the Silk Road Economic Belt in Kazakhstan in September 2013; a month later, in Indonesia he proposed the Maritime Silk Road (Miller, 2017, pp. 30-31). Obviously, the Belt part of the initiative is more important for CA. From China's perspective, some suggest that the primary regional goal is maintenance of security and stability in its own province Xinjiang which can be ensured by developing the adjacent CA (Cooley, 2012, pp. 74-75). Notably, Alexander Cooley interpreted Chinese regional policy in this way in 2012 when the BRI hadn't even been announced yet. After effectively asserting tight control over its populous coastal lands, China has turned to the western part, where security and development issues aren't solved yet. Central Asia represents a cobweb of security, geopolitics, economy and development issues. China certainly demonstrates willingness to untie this cobweb and has flexible approach in its policies towards CA. The BRI, despite its currently vague structure, has become the most discussed vision of the future that should benefit the region as well as regional powers.

1.4.2. Geopolitics

The paramount product of Chinese institutional geopolitics – Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) has much wider range of objectives besides military cooperation than NATO. In its scope, the SCO is similar to the Organization of Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE). However, China promotes the idea of mutual benefits from cooperation without interference into internal political affairs. But there is still a mixed attitude towards Chinese expansion in CA as a lingering legacy of Soviet propaganda (Miller, 2017, pp. 167-168). Yet the SCO has been extensively used as a power projection of China in CA. The SCO agreements on military cooperation practically allow People's Liberation Army to deploy abroad for joint military exercises or security maintenance especially along the Tajik-

Afghan border.³⁰ China has also started building military facilities in the region. For instance, an outpost in Tajikistan close to the border with Afghanistan was secretly built in recent years, but Tajik and Chinese governments officially deny its existence.³¹ On the other hand, neither SCO nor CSTO showed will or desire to solve the Kyrgyz-Tajik border clashes in 2021 and 2022, which could be suggestive of the institutions' prioritized objective to serve the goals of Beijing and Moscow. But the Kyrgyz and Tajik governments are not interested to solve the dispute either, but regularly use it in populist manner to consolidate power.³² Populism has flourished as a practice and transformed into a trait of local political culture. China's top security objective is to tackle terrorism, extremism and separatism threats from Afghanistan; therefore, it closely cooperates with Tajikistan and provides generous military aid in terms of infrastructure, finance, equipment and training.³³ Definitely, Tajikistan benefits from this cooperation by militarizing itself, besides, bolstered Tajik military forces effectively stay under the local government commandment. Arguably, the Kyrgyz-Tajik clash in September 2022 involved troops, who have participated in those trainings and equipped with Chinese help.³⁴ As a result, the paradox arises as China attempts to enhance security in the region, local powers exploit Chinese military assistance in their domestic interests and, consequently, weaken regional security. Such behavior is one of the distinguishing characteristics of local politics.

1.4.3. Development

After the Soviet Union dissolution, Central Asia found itself in the category of landlocked developing countries (LLDCs). This category is infected with dismal economic performance, low population density and distant location from the global trade (Chowdhury & Erdenebileg, 2006, pp. 3-13). Central Asian oil and gas have always attracted investors, and China has been acquiring fields and building pipelines leading to its mainland. Since

³⁰ Janik, Sierra (November 12, 2020): The Shanghai Cooperation Organization: A Testbed for Chinese Power Projection. US-China Economic and Security Review Commission, <https://www.uscc.gov/research/shanghai-cooperation-organization-testbed-chinese-power-projection>, retrieved January 31, 2023.

³¹ Standish, Reid (October 14, 2021): From a Secret Base in Tajikistan, China's War on Terror Adjusts to a New Reality. Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty, <https://gandhara.rferl.org/a/tajikistan-china-war-on-terror-afghan/31509370.html>, retrieved December 7, 2022.

³² Doolotkeldieva, Asel – Marat, Erica (October 4, 2022): Why Russia and China Aren't Intervening in Central Asia. Foreign Policy Magazine, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2022/10/04/tajikistan-kyrgyzstan-russia-china-intervention-central-asia/>, retrieved January 31, 2023.

³³ Kizilay, Seyma (December 2, 2022): Tajikistan-China Military Cooperation. Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies, <https://www.ankasam.org/tajikistan-china-military-cooperation/?lang=en>, retrieved February 24, 2023.

³⁴ Urciuolo, Luca (September 29, 2022): Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan: causes and analysis of an endless border dispute. SpecialEurasia, <https://www.specialeurasia.com/2022/09/29/kyrgyzstan-tajikistan-borders/>, retrieved February 23, 2023.

2011 China has been the main consumer of the Turkmen gas overtaking Russia hegemony and increasing export diversification (Bohr, 2016, p. 77). Chinese corporations are often distinguished as good customers, who are willing to play according to local corrupt rules and strictly follow their own non-interference policy. Besides gas and oil, China has been buying uranium for its nuclear plants from Kazakhstan (Peyrouse, 2007, pp. 32-33). Notably, 45% of world uranium production came from Kazakhstan's mines in 2021.³⁵ Undoubtedly, natural resource dependency blended with agonizing corruption doesn't contribute to development. Unlike natural resource sector, trade sector employs more people, facilitates liberal political environment and market economy and encourages strengthening of civil society. For instance, impoverished Kyrgyzstan liberalized its economy, joined the WTO in 1998 and started trading with China (Tian, 2018, pp. 31-32). The result has been creation of other business sectors, entrepreneurship development and trade hubs such as a giant Dordoi bazaar near Bishkek (Ibid). An indiscriminatory analysis of the Chinese trade with CA allows to infer that cheap, low quality goods are actually beneficial since they are affordable and can satisfy the needs of the post-Soviet Asian LLDCs (Peyrouse, 2007, p. 71). Chinese factor in CA, thus, has different effects. On the one hand, China simply exploits natural resources which barely has positive impact on internal sustainable development, on the other hand, the BRI, trade and investments actually have potential to give inertia to development in the landlocked, low-income region, which is often neglected by international community. The BRI, though, should not be viewed as the origin of the Chinese involvement in development of CA. Even before the Initiative, China has been heavily investing in the region's communication infrastructure and telecommunications. Especially poor mountainous Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan benefited from reconstruction and rehabilitation of roads, railways, tunnels as well as modernization of its telecommunication by cheap Chinese credits (Ibid, pp. 30-45).

Chapter conclusion

Regional powers are actively involved in Central Asia. In many cases, they utilize ethnic links and historical ties as political tools. Besides hard power, they exercise soft power tactics to appeal and build good relations with the region. Development in CA, despite considerable external investments, natural resource wealth and inherited solid HDI indicators, has stagnated or even rolled back. The reasons are numerous but besides

³⁵ World Nuclear Association (2022): World Uranium Mining Production. World Nuclear Association, <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/mining-of-uranium/world-uranium-mining-production.aspx>, retrieved March 31, 2023.

geopolitics and inescapable landlocked geography, local political culture has been playing a crucial role. Militarization, clientelism, power consolidation, obsession with security and sovereignty, corruption, anti-West and anti-Chinese moods dominate the politics. Central Asia is certainly not founded on the Western principles and ideals, local political culture sets the rules of the geopolitical game. Undoubtedly, local political elites have mastered using political culture for their benefit. Regional powers reign in CA but local powers rule in the region. The objective of this chapter has been to give a general idea of the region and introduce the regional actors.

2 CHAPTER: THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Geopolitics and development have been exhaustively studied since the end of the Second World War. Nowadays, geopolitics is not limited to only geography, and development is not only about economic growth. For example, Human Development Reports website of UNDP bases its approach on the works of a Nobel laureate Amartya Sen, who stated that development is a set of freedoms; the institution also considers a GDP per capita as an inadequate measurement unit for development.³⁶ When Halford Mackinder presented his draft paper on Heartland to the Royal Geographical Society in January, 1904, a prophetic critique came from Leo Amery, a British politician, stating that people with industrial power would defeat all others and a geographical position wouldn't matter (Blouet, 2005, p. 9). Amery was impressed with the first flight of Wright Brothers in the USA just a few weeks ago and that historical event even more solidified his belief in the technology and industrialization as the source of power.

Further analysis requires formulation of practical definitions for geopolitics and development, and categorization of each definition. A brief analytical study of selected literature on geopolitics and development is followed by Paul Collier's analysis. His definitions are used as a theoretical base for categorization. Collier outlines four types of traps: conflict trap, natural resource trap, landlocked with bad neighbors and bad governance in a small country. When a country falls into one of these traps, its development process stagnates or even reverses. He also analyzes four types of instruments that could help to alleviate or even free from the traps: aid, military intervention, laws and Trade. Collier is an economist, and his perspective is different from that of a political expert. He actually considers a military intervention as a solution in some cases, but doesn't take into account a

³⁶ Human Development Reports (n.d.): What is Human Development? HDR UNDP official website, <https://hdr.undp.org/about/human-development>, retrieved February 2, 2023.

possible geopolitical escalation from such an intervention. Notably, Collier didn't use the word geopolitics at all in his book, but his instruments are geopolitical tools as the analysis reveals and confirms below.

2.1 Geopolitics

The proper start of the study is the popular theories during the Age of Imperialism. Halford Mackinder's (1861-1947) Heartland, Nicholas John Spykman's (1893-1943) Rimland and Friedrich Ratzel's (1844-1904) Lebensraum were all the products of classical geopolitics thinking, which puts emphasis on geography. Alfred Thayer Mahan's (1840-1914) Sea Power partly deviates from geographic origin of geopolitics and advocates for domination in the sea by building a technologically superior navy. Geopolitical thinking penetrated the strategies of 20th century leaders, the most notable is Hitler's vision of Lebensraum for Germany. Mahan's emphasis on building a capable navy motivated the US to challenge British Royal Navy domination. Spykman's Rimland was widely read by the Americans and prepared them for the post-war world where the West would be occupied with containing the Soviet Union (Blouet, 2005, p. 6). Germany, the latecomer into the partition of the world, nevertheless, accounted as one of the most industrialized European powers, could only expand at the expense of other European powers and predominantly in one direction – to the east.³⁷ Resulting in two World Wars, German imperial ambitions not only ended the Age of Imperialism but also demonstrated a destructive effect of imperial geopolitics.

After two devastating World Wars as a result of imperialistic obsession of European powers, the West finally realized that such a world order is detrimental in its nature and the risks for security and stability are unquestionably high. The Marshall Plan was dedicated for reconstruction of Europe. Analogous initiative for the rest of the world was the Truman Doctrine, which deliberately locked the foreign policy of the USA for the next several decades as the Western assistance to developing states threatened by external and internal authoritarian forces.³⁸ But there were some thinkers that opposed such intervention of the West. The most influential thinker was Immanuel Wallerstein (1930-2019) who criticized interventionism by the capitalist West. His conviction is based on the studies of the European colonization history, where he found the roots of the Western interventionism as a self-proclaimed moral right and a divine civilizing mission (Wallerstein, 2006, pp. 1-29). The

³⁷ Overly, Richard (December 4, 2020): In search of Lebensraum. Engelsberg Ideas, <https://engelsbergideas.com/essays/in-search-of-lebensraum/>, retrieved November 18, 2022.

³⁸ US Department of State Archive (n.d.): The Truman Doctrine, 1947. US Department of State Archive, <https://2001-2009.state.gov/r/pa/ho/time/cwr/82210.htm>, retrieved December 29, 2022.

encoded message in his famous Core-Periphery model is a criticism of the exploitative behavior of the West that continues to this day as neocolonialism.

The modern definition of geopolitics still revolves around geography, power and survival. Kaplan openly defends realist roots of geopolitics for its rationality in predicting the future. Realist theories certainly have hardline proponents in the US mainly known as the Hawks. According to this recap of geopolitics, any type of external intervention is an act dictated by self-interest and core instincts of an external actor to survive and prosper. Therefore, even such soft-power instruments as aid, assistance, international laws and trade possess geopolitical nucleus, whereas military intervention is undoubtedly a geopolitical tool. Another parallel of Kaplan's perspective with this thesis is his concentration on four main emerging powers: China, Russia, Turkey and Iran (Kaplan, 2018, p. 10). Such formulation fits the objective of the thesis to study the impact of geopolitics on the development of Central Asia because it allows to identify actors and motives behind their activities. Robert Kaplan is an ardent proponent of geopolitics, he argues that the geopolitical challenges should be responded symmetrically, in other words, the USA and its allies should consider every instrument at their disposal in order to tackle a problem. Other popular proponents of active geopolitics are Walter Russel Mead, Jakub Grygiel and Parag Khanna.

The quintessential nature of geopolitics is about interference into other states' affairs, and scholars mainly argue about the pros and cons of such interference. How do powers intervene and what tools do they use? Paul Collier discusses four instruments that the powers can use to assist the countries that are struggling to develop. But those instruments can essentially be used with geopolitical motives.

2.1.1 Military intervention

A military intervention is a classic geopolitical practice. The scale of intervention can also differ greatly. Russian invasion of Ukraine involves more than 200,000 soldiers, and CSTO peacekeeping operation in Kazakhstan in January 2022 involved a couple of thousand soldiers. Nevertheless, military intervention for purpose of peacekeeping or deterrence can positively impact on security and subsequently on development. The USA maintains around 120 bases and over 50,000 troops in Japan according to journalistic estimates.³⁹ This allowed Japan to concentrate on development and become a success story of the Western military intervention for security and peace preservation.

³⁹ Hussein, Mohammed – Haddad, Mohammed (September 10, 2021): Infographic: US military presence around the world. Al Jazeera, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/10/infographic-us-military-presence-around-the-world-interactive>, retrieved October 25, 2022.

A military intervention is costly but it is very effective in short-run to reach negative peace. For instance, the intervention of the British troops in Sierra Leone in 2000 to tackle the advancement of the Revolutionary United Front rebels is referred as a success case of military intervention (Collier, 2007, p. 127). The overhead costs of this geopolitical tool are substantial, for instance, the Department of Defense is the largest US government agency with a budget of 752,9 billion US dollars. It divides the world into six parts and assigns each a Combatant Command.⁴⁰ Central Asia falls into the Central Command (CENTCOM) area of responsibility. CENTCOM outlines its priorities as: 1. Deter Iran, 2. Counter violent extremist organizations, 3. Compete strategically, 4. Regional constructs, 5. Integrated air and missile defense/counter unmanned aerial systems.⁴¹ Military expenditures are a stress on economy if spent above a certain threshold, therefore military intervention is a tool affordable for big economies. Although the total expenditures of the US are more than those of the Security Council members combined, it is actually Russia leading in terms of expenditures as a share of GDP. In general, militarization is the strongest in the Middle East with Oman spending over 7% of its GDP on military expenditures in 2021 (SIPRI).

Figure 3: Military expenditure of Security Council members, Iran, India and Turkey in 2021

Source: own editing, data source: SIPRI (n.d.): SIPRI Military Expenditure Database. Stockholm International Peace Research Institute <https://www.sipri.org/databases/milex>, retrieved March 11, 2023.

The last and most important aspect of a military intervention is picking a side in a conflict. The US State Department tends to assist a side that struggles against authoritarian rule or demonstrates willingness for democratization, however, the Pentagon and CIA often covertly cooperate with authoritarian regimes. Russia and China intervene to assist the loyal

⁴⁰ U.S. Department of Defense (2022): <https://www.defense.gov/About/>, retrieved November 17, 2022.

⁴¹ The U.S. Central Command (2022): <https://www.centcom.mil/ABOUT-US/COMMAND-PRIORITIES/>, retrieved November 17, 2022.

authoritarian governments against religious or ethnic minorities. Russian CSTO Contingent of peacekeeping troops and Chinese CSO Regional Anti-terrorist Structure (RATS) primarily work with the governments and assist them in maintaining national and regional security. The problem is that the governments can label undesirable elements as threats to security in order to activate and legitimize military intervention through these organizations. CSTO troops intervened in Kazakhstan in January 2022, when the protests jeopardized the Kazakh regime. Conclusively, this geopolitical tool is extremely effective in the hands of governments, therefore, contrary to Collier's expectations that it brings sustainable peace which is fundamental for development, military intervention is used to guarantee regime survival in Central Asia.

2.1.2 International laws, agreements and rules

International laws, agreements and rules that are promoted or enforced by powerful states are considered to set up a sustainable and secure environment for people, businesses and nature. The adjective 'international' doesn't imply global, but there are certain laws, agreements and standards that are adopted by several countries. Collier gives an example of Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI). This body has an objective to promote an open and accountable management of oil, gas and mineral resources.⁴² The membership is voluntary; Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan from Central Asia participate in the initiative. EITI standards are not enforced, and a corrupt government is not motivated to promote transparency since it inhibits their ability to enrich themselves. Corruption is part of local rules and political culture that overrides international laws. Thus, although Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan are incredibly corrupt countries, multinational corporations still operate there. Human rights, environment, labor, health standards deteriorate in the opaque environment of extractive industries. The oil and gas fields of Kazakhstan are located in sparsely populated areas, and it is even more tempting to violate laws there because the voices of remote small communities are rarely heard.⁴³

A more descriptive example of an international law is the Vienna Document 2011 on Confidence- and Security-building measures. The participating states in OSCE are subjects to abide and follow this document. The main objective of the document is to build and enhance security in the world. An OSCE state must share its military information and most

⁴² Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (n.d.): Our mission. EITI, <https://eiti.org/our-mission>, retrieved March 1, 2023.

⁴³ Reynolds, Ashley Nancy (August 3, 2021): Opinion: Kazakhstan's oil sector is rife with human rights abuses. The Third Pole, <https://www.thethirdpole.net/en/energy/kazakhstans-oil-sector-is-rife-with-human-rights-abuses/>, retrieved February 16, 2023.

importantly report about military exercises in advance.⁴⁴ Although Russia is an OSCE state, it deliberately misreported about its military drills in 2008 prior invading Georgia.⁴⁵ The Russian report understated the number of troops, thus, violating the article 40.3.1. which declares that prior report is required if the number of troops participating in a planned military exercise is at least 9000. If a country is not in the OSCE, it is not obliged to abide these rules. This refers to China and Iran that are not members of the organization.

With the 2022 invasion of Ukraine by Russia, it is necessary to analyze sanctions as an example of international laws and conditions. The arsenal of the West is broad from embargos, restrictions on financial activity, travel, business and so on. Russia has been cut off from the Western goods and technologies; it can't acquire them through direct trade. But there is a way to partially evade this embargo by buying necessary technologies through loyal or dependent partners. Kazakhstan has been actively evading sanctions and trading with Russia, and yet Kazakhstan hasn't faced any serious consequences.⁴⁶ If sanctions can be considered as a stick, partnership agreements in return for assistance are a carrot. NATO Partnership for Peace (PfP) established in 1994 offer a range of cooperation areas. PfP also implicitly hints on generous financial assistance and the geopolitical difference from regular type of assistance is in the conditions. This program seems to be designed specifically for post-Soviet countries according to its year of establishment and the list of members.

The conditions for obtaining loans and credits from international organizations or Western countries are also a type of international standards. For example, in order to apply for assistance from International Monetary Fund (IMF), a country has to follow a set of rules and satisfy the IMF conditionality. Such policies imply that a borrowing country has to conduct reforms in many sectors and report to the IMF.⁴⁷ In the period from 1990 to 2010, IMF and WB were the main sources of loans, and Central Asian poor countries had been heavily borrowing which led to unsustainable indebtedness. The Kyrgyz public opinion was

⁴⁴ OSCE Forum for Security Co-operation (November 30, 2011): Vienna Document 2011 on Confidence- and Security-building measures. OSCE, <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/4/86597.pdf>, retrieved February 13, 2023.

⁴⁵ Johnson, Dave (December 14, 2017): ZAPAD 2017 and Euro-Atlantic security. NATO Review, <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/articles/2017/12/14/zapad-2017-and-euro-atlantic-security/index.html>, retrieved November 3, 2022.

⁴⁶ Burna-Asefi, Sophia Nina (February 27, 2023): Just Passing Through: Kazakhstan's Parallel Trade Predicament, <https://thediplomat.com/2023/02/just-passing-through-kazakhstans-parallel-trade-predicament/>, retrieved March 3, 2023.

⁴⁷ IMF (February 22, 2021): IMF Conditionality. IMF, <https://www.imf.org/en/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/02/21/28/IMF-Conditionality#:~:text=When%20a%20country%20borrows%20from,able%20to%20repay%20the%20IMF> retrieved February 13, 2023.

harshly against the conditions to restructure national debt when it was estimated that it exceeded sustainable levels. The Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) initiative by WB and IMF was harshly criticized as the Western interference into domestic affairs by enforcing vague reforms according to the protestors.⁴⁸ Technically, debt restructuring is a common practice, however, it sparks anti-Western sentiments and opposition in public, thus, obtaining undesirable geopolitical contours. In other cases, political elites of recipient countries realized that the Western conditions for assistance can be easily cheated since “they only needed to promise to reform, not actually do it” in order to keep receiving assistance (Collier, 2007, p. 67).

China has seized an opportunity in this divergence between the developing world and the West. It has created its own institutions and set up its own rules and conditions to challenge the Western counterparts. Furthermore, China understands that the nature of international laws and institutions gives a certain advantage to the Western organizations. For example, as of February 13, 2023, the voting share of China in the IMF Board of Governors was 6.08% of total, which is a little less than Japanese 6.14% and dwarfed by the US 16.5%.⁴⁹ If all Western countries’ votes are added including the Japanese ones, that even further diminishes the power of China in the IMF decision making procedure. Why does China have to restrain its economic power when it can actually create its own institutions to rival the Western terms and rules? Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank is a copy of Asian Development Bank; New Development Bank was set up in 2015 by Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (BRICS) to facilitate investments in sustainable development including the BRI projects; but the majority of money is distributed through China Development Bank and China Exim Bank (Miller, 2017, pp. 34-39). The Chinese conditions are easy, and such strategy helps China to build relations with developing countries and facilitate its geopolitical strategy.

International laws, rules, agreements and standards can set up a friendly and transparent environment provided that the international community adheres to them. But the reality is that the developing countries see these conditions as a Western attempt to manipulate and create a favorable environment to project their own interests. Moreover, regional powers have shown capability in building their own alternatives to international laws. In a few cases discussed above, they could effectively use laws and standards against the West. Such a

⁴⁸ Committee for the Abolition of Illegitimate Debt (January 30, 2007): Kyrgyz Protesters Target World Bank Debt Scheme, https://www.cadtm.org/spip.php?page=imprimer&id_article=2420, retrieved February 18, 2023.

⁴⁹ IMF (February 13, 2023): IMF Members' Quotas and Voting Power, and IMF Board of Governors. IMF, <https://www.imf.org/en/About/executive-board/members-quotas#U>, retrieved February 13, 2023.

competitive behavior of powers effectively turns laws, agreements and standards into the tools that are extensively used in geopolitics.

2.1.3 Aid

Aid, despite its explicit humanitarian purpose, can also be implicitly used as a geopolitical tool. It can be considered as a soft power but the political dividends on the international arena can be substantial. For instance, Central Asian dependency on Russia in energy subsidies and remittances as well as historical ties grants Russia political advantage in the international arena. Consequently, for instance, four out of the five countries abstained and Turkmenistan did not vote at all on the UN resolution on October 12, 2022 related to legibility of the referendums on the annexed Ukrainian territories by Russia.⁵⁰ In overwhelming number of cases, foreign aid is a geopolitical tool with embedded interest of a donor state. In the letter addressed to the US Senate and the House of Representatives, the US Global Leadership Coalition (2017) states that:

“The State Department, USAID, Millennium Challenge Corporation, Peace Corps and other development agencies are critical to preventing conflict and reducing the need to put our men and women in uniform in harm’s way. As Secretary James Mattis said while Commander of U.S. Central Command, “If you don’t fully fund the State Department, then I need to buy more ammunition.” The military will lead the fight against terrorism on the battlefield, but it needs strong civilian partners in the battle against the drivers of extremism— lack of opportunity, insecurity, injustice, and hopelessness.”⁵¹

Poor countries have always depended on external assistance. Tajikistan’s budget was vitally dependent on subsidies from Moscow during the Soviet Era, in this sense, Tajikistan could hardly be considered as economically sovereign. Obviously, after the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Tajikistan plunged into a humanitarian crisis, which only exacerbated food and basic commodities security (Foltz, 2019, pp. 185-186). Official development assistance (ODA) doesn’t have to be repaid. Rich countries comprising Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) provide ODA to developing countries in order to curb instability and enhance security. The members generally commit to allocate a certain amount

⁵⁰ UN News (October 12, 2022): Ukraine: UN General Assembly demands Russia reverse course on ‘attempted illegal annexation’. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/10/1129492>, retrieved October 30, 2022.

⁵¹ The US Global Leadership Coalition (February 27, 2017): A letter to Speaker Ryan, Minority Leader Pelosi, Majority Leader McConnell, and Minority Leader Schumer. https://www.usglc.org/downloads/2017/02/FY18_International_Affairs_Budget_House_Senate.pdf, retrieved February 12, 2023/

to aid, which is agreed around 0,7% of GNI, however, actual average is around 0,4%; in addition to aid, debt cancellation is also considered as ODA (OECD, 2003). However, such big economies as China and India are not OECD members, which suggests that these countries can arrange their own strategy on foreign aid assistance. There is no reliable data on aid from non-OECD countries, but it is rational to assume that the share of Chinese assistance to Central Asian countries have been increasing. Currently, ODA from OECD countries to Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan fluctuates between 5-10% of GNI, which can be even higher as a percentage of national budget.

Figure 4: Official Development Assistance from OECD received as % of GNI

Source: own editing, data source: (The World Bank), Net ODA received (% of GNI) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/DT.ODA.ODAT.GN.ZS>, retrieved on February 11, 2023.

Paul Collier doesn't discuss military assistance in his book, but OECD considers it as a type of ODA. The difference between military assistance and military intervention is clear as the latter refers to physical presence of foreign troops. Such aid is usually provided on bilateral basis. The local governments usually prefer military assistance since it helps to strengthen forces under its command. The West as well as regional powers often provide assistance especially to those countries that border with hot spots or experience internal instability. For instance, the US eased restrictions on providing assistance to Uzbekistan in order to increase cooperation on security matters related to Afghanistan, despite the fact that the Uzbek government has been condemned for corruption and human rights violations (Cooley, 2012, p. 48). The latest military assistance to Uzbekistan was presented in 2022 in form of 50

Polaris MRZR light tactical combat mobility vehicles valued at 2,8 million US\$.⁵² The US expects that this assistance will help to enhance regional security, but there is no guarantee that these vehicles will not be used against political opposition within Uzbekistan or quell sporadic unrests in Karakalpakstan Autonomous Republic. Notably, the violent suppression of protests in July of 2022 in Karakalpakstan clearly demonstrated that the Uzbek security forces are not restrained to use lethal force if there is a perceived threat to national sovereignty and security.⁵³

The positive effect of aid is neutralized by corruptness and greed of a recipient government. The objective of aid is to help a poor country, and the flow of gratuitous assistance stops when a country becomes self-subsistent. Logically, a recipient government has no interest in declaring a progress in development. It has already become a custom for corrupt governments to acquire aid by exaggerating their security and development problems. Such misuse of aid doesn't go unnoticed in the donor countries. Even the USA politics have been infected with populism over foreign aid asking why this money couldn't be spent domestically. Especially Donald Trump's populist rhetoric won American public opinion during his presidency, but the Congress rejected slashes on foreign aid because they view aid to other countries as serving US interests.⁵⁴ Apart from populism, aid has always been positioned as a geopolitical tool as it is intended to enhance domestic security and promote interests of a donor state.

But aid is extremely effective in developing a strong civil society if it reaches the intended recipients directly. Such aid can come in forms of foreign experts, advisors, organizations conducting lectures, civil trainings and even foreign education. People suspected in linking with foreign assistance are labeled as foreign agents. When Vladimir Putin became president after Dmitry Medvedev, a profoundly prohibitive legislation on foreign agents was adopted in Russia in 2012, a few years later, a similar legislation was discussed in Kyrgyzstan. This legislation limits and violates rights of anyone suspected of having ties with the West.⁵⁵ Such determination to reject the Western 'influence' is partly a result of Putin's fears to lose power

⁵² U.S. Mission Uzbekistan (October 26, 2022): United States Presents Military Equipment to Uzbekistan's Ministry of Defense. U.S. Embassy in Uzbekistan, <https://uz.usembassy.gov/united-states-presents-military-equipment-to-uzbekistans-ministry-of-defense/>, retrieved February 18, 2023.

⁵³ Imamova, Navbahor (November 11, 2022): Uzbekistan Asked to Allow Foreign Experts to Investigate Unrest in Karakalpakstan. Voice of America, <https://www.voanews.com/a/uzbekistan-asked-to-allow-foreign-experts-to-investigate-unrest-in-karakalpakstan/6829826.html>, retrieved February 18, 2023.

⁵⁴ Cohen Raphael S. (December 30, 2020): Why We 'Send Them Money'. The RAND Corporation, <https://www.rand.org/blog/2020/12/why-we-send-them-money.html>, retrieved February 12, 2023.

⁵⁵ Machalek, Katherine (n.d.): Factsheet: Russia's NGO Laws. Freedom House, https://freedomhouse.org/sites/default/files/Fact%20Sheet_0.pdf, retrieved January 23, 2023.

but, in general, foreign assistance of a such type is indeed an effective instrument in confronting authoritarian regimes.⁵⁶

Aid and assistance as a geopolitical instrument have evolved in scope and efficiency. Revisionist powers, especially Russia, have realized its ability to stimulate changes within a sovereign state without a single troop on the ground. During Euromaidan in Ukraine in December 2013, Victoria Nuland – the State Department representative – walked to the protestors and gave them some snack. This event was broadcasted on the Russian state TV channel and interpreted as the US interference into domestic affairs of a sovereign state. Nuland’s cookies, also referred as the State Department’s cookies, has become a popular geopolitical meme for the US assistance and interference in the post-Soviet states.⁵⁷ Such ‘cookies’ have proved its effectiveness as Ukraine drifted away from the Russian influence.

2.1.4 Trade

Trade is a very tricky aspect for analysis in terms of geopolitics because it is fixed in the minds of many as a soft power. Certainly, the origins of trade lie in the reciprocally beneficial exchange of values between parties. However, trade in the modern world is used as a geopolitical tool as Russia has already proved in practice with gas exports to Europe. Paul Collier is positive that trade can help lagging countries to catch up with the rest of the world provided that the rich countries conduct trade liberalization and abolish tariffs for poor countries. This strategy might work for African countries, but the situation in Central Asia is different. The region has a burden of landlocked-ness which, in more specific terms, means that high cost of transportation inhibits exports more than tariff barriers (Chowdhury & Erdenebileg, 2006, pp. 18-19). Chinese BRI aims to solve transportation issue and also has a long-term vision that trade facilitation should help to integrate restive Xinjiang (Miller, 2017, pp. 49-53). In other words, China has a grand plan to enhance security by developing economy through trade. Third issue is the scramble for natural resources of the region. Therefore, trade in the context of Central Asia should be analyzed as a multidimensional geopolitical tool that targets three main issues.

Central Asian states are subsistence economies, whose export mainly rely on commodity products. Examination of the region’s main items for export confirms regional dependency

⁵⁶ Lipman, Maria (March 13, 2015): How Russia has come to loathe the West. European Council on Foreign Relations, https://ecfr.eu/article/commentary_how_russia_has_come_to_loathe_the_west311346/, retrieved January 22, 2023.

⁵⁷ Akinchenko, Mihail (April 21, 2019): Za proshedshie pjat' let fraza «pechen'ki Nuland» stala ne menea ustojchivoj, chem «30 srebrenikov». First Channel, https://www.1tv.ru/news/2019-04-21/363944-za_proshedshie_pyat_let_fraza_pechenki_nuland_stala_ne_menea_ustoychivoy_chem_30_srebrenikov, retrieved March 11, 2023.

on commodity products. The Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC) platform shows that CA export is overwhelmingly occupied by natural resources such as petroleum, gas, gold and aluminum as well as unprocessed agricultural products such as cotton, dried legumes and barley. In return, the region imports fuel, fabrics, apparel and machinery. The most devastating situation is in the trade of Turkmenistan where natural gas was 76.5% of exports in 2020 and the main trade partner was China importing 98.8% of that gas.⁵⁸ With such advantageous terms in trade with the region, China is rationally prone to preserve these trade relations for as long as possible. Even the Western countries change their fair-trade rhetoric to predatory tactics in order to exploit cheap natural resources in Central Asia. The UK bought 99.8% of Kyrgyzstan's gold export, which comprised 65.4% of total exports; and Switzerland bought 99.8% of Tajikistan's gold, which was 48% of total exports in 2020.⁵⁹ Thus, Central Asian governments depend on natural resource export and have no incentive to stimulate other industries. Moreover, local technology-intensive industries and manufacturing can't compete against cheap alternatives flooding as import, and, consequently, remain in embryonic stage of development. Trade between unequal partners is rarely fair, and it is always tempting for a stronger partner to use it as a geopolitical tool for domination.

China is also interested in geostrategic position of the region for its grand BRI. CA is a transit territory of the trade flow between China and Europe. Obviously, this overland trade route represents only a tiny fraction of massive maritime route, but even that small fraction has a potential to completely reshape the region. Another chronic problem of the region is inferior infrastructure which always receives insufficient investment (Chowdhury & Erdenebileg, 2006, pp. 6-10). This vicious circle can be broken, if the BRI proves to be successful and sustainable in the long-run. The export of CA could reach other markets and become more competitive, while China could gain geopolitically by enhancing security within and outside its borders. Trade is a geopolitical instrument which can help to achieve security objectives in an unconventional way and doesn't cause radical opposition and hostility.

The four discussed instruments of Paul Collier can also be used as geopolitical tools. Military intervention can be effective in dealing with conflicts but it is costly and requires technical capabilities. Moreover, keeping troops abroad can generate even more expenses. Although this tool can bring peace, further development should be overtaken by other instruments. Aid

⁵⁸ OEC (n.d.): Turkmenistan. The Observatory of Economic Complexity, <https://oec.world/en/profile/country/tkm>, retrieved February 16, 2023.

⁵⁹ Ibid (n.d.): Kyrgyzstan., Tajikistan.

also has a geopolitical characteristic since such assistance is mainly provided to the states that are politically or ideologically compatible. The West supports the governments that promise to nurture democratic principles, China, on the other hand, tends to provide assistance on the basis of reciprocal respect and non-interference in sovereign matters. But recipient states as seen in the example of Central Asian countries can adapt to imposed conditions in order to keep receiving aid and assistance. International laws are usually less effective in the countries where the Rule of Law is weak and violated. Trade is the most multifunctional geopolitical tool that allows a power to achieve several goals, but in order to use it effectively, a power should have export-oriented economy with large-scale production. The four geopolitical tools can be used simultaneously or complement each other.

2.2 Development

Development sphere has mostly been dominated by economists. A legendary economist scholar – Walt Whitman Rostow (1916-2003) – touched the issue of development even before it was a trend. His modernization theory explores how a traditional society can reach the age of high mass consumption. Rostow's theory is about internal sources and forces of modernization, however, there is an important political decision that should be taken when the state reaches economic maturity: welfare, consumption or power on the world scene (Rostow, 1959, p. 11). The USA concentrated on consumption and Germany concentrated on power enhancement. Therefore, according to Rostow, a development process largely relies on conscious political decision and commitment within that country.

The next prominent economist, whose contribution to development has been fundamental, is Amartya Sen. His work is central to UNDP largely because his approach is more holistic and expands beyond economics. Sen (2000) identifies five types of freedoms and discusses them in a philosophical manner: political freedom, economic facilities, social opportunities, transparency guarantees and protective security. His most relevant argument to this research is interconnection between democracy (part of political freedom) to economic growth. In general, there are three main arguments against political freedom – first, democracy hampers economic growth, second, poor people tend to choose fulfillment of economic needs rather than having political freedom, and, third, political freedom and democracy are overwhelmingly 'Western' priority and doesn't fit in the so-called Asian values (Sen, 2000, pp. 148-149). These arguments are put forward by authoritarian governments of developing states. Especially, the third argument is widely used in Central Asia and remains as a part of local political culture.

In order to check this assumption, a brief quantitative analysis has been conducted and the results are presented in the Figure 5 and explained below. The relationship between economic growth and democracy is directly proportional meaning that the bigger economies in the world also have higher democracy indexes. But the same relationship is inversely proportional in the LLDCs; bigger economies in this group demonstrate lower democracy indexes. Such a discrepancy is not coincidental and demonstrates resistance of authoritarian governments of LLDCs to democratization since this will eventually increase transparency and curb corruption and illegal enrichment. Thus, the government generally advocates against democracy by portraying it as a Western hazardous element incompatible with local values and traditions. Unfortunately, this argument is very successful in CA, and that is one of the reasons why the public is so resilient to democratization.

The sympathy for a strong leader, who can singlehandedly solve problems and overcome challenges lingers in the remote impoverished communities, which comprise the majority of electorate. Economic development without adequate democracy is more known as the Chinese model. A strong state guidance and intentional deprivation of political and human freedoms is known as Lee thesis – the definition comes as acknowledgement of Singaporean dictator Lee Kuan Yew. But Amartya Sen (2000, pp. 15-16) rejects the hypothesis that authoritarian regimes can provide better economic performance than more liberal ones.

Central Asia leans towards authoritarianism. The effect of this political characteristic is that currently all five Central Asian states are presidential republics where the head of the state faces no real opposition and tightly controls all three branches of power. Turkmenistan and Tajikistan have descended even further into authoritarianism by converting the state into a family business inherited from father to son. Short-lived parliamentarism in Kyrgyzstan ended in 2021, when a chaotic referendum approved changes to the constitution effectively turning the state into presidential republic (Engvall, 2022, pp. 97-98).

Figure 5: GDP and Democracy normality of the world and abnormality in LLDCs

Source: *own analysis, data source: (1) (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2022). Democracy Index 2021**. Economist Intelligence Unit, <https://pages.eiu.com/rs/753-RIO-438/images/eiu-democracy-index-2021.pdf>, retrieved on February 20, 2023. (2) (The World Bank), GDP (current US\$) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>, retrieved on February 20, 2023.

*The analysis involves 2019 data on 154 states and visualization on the graphs with exponential trendlines. The US and China are excluded from the graph because their projection visually stretches the first graph of the Figure 5. The exclusion doesn't distort the general trend. Therefore, the biggest economy on the first graph is Japan.

Y-axis - The higher the number the more democratic the country

X-axis - The higher the number the bigger the economy

A considerable gap in the ideas of Sen, as seen from the perspective of this thesis, is neglect of effects of geography and local political culture on development. His argument in favor of development is positioned as the social good of the highest value. Nevertheless, Sen fails to persuasively explain why some countries develop at a slower rate or even roll back, why some countries are tolerant to authoritarian regimes. Moreover, there is no extensive analysis of the effect of the neighboring states and regional powers in his theory.

Paul Collier, whose analysis is central to this thesis, is also an acknowledged economist. He also advances further than the field of economics in his study of development challenges. Collier labels those challenges as traps and below is the brief analysis of each trap. This research employs Collier's analysis and tests it on Central Asia. Interestingly, Collier mentioned CA in his book but concentrated mostly on Sub-Saharan and Southeastern Asia, therefore, this research will be a valuable addition to his analysis. Another strong assumption in the book that harmonizes with this research is that a trapped country is not capable of developing without external assistance from another country or international community. This assumption sets a perfect environment where the impact of geopolitics on development can be observed and tested. Central Asia is a much more convenient region for analyzing the traps than Sub-Saharan region. The size of the region and the number of states perfectly fit for analysis. The analysis of each trap below aims to give general idea of Collier.

2.2.1 Conflict trap

Any conflict negatively affects development and there are numerous sources of it. From the political science perspective, nationalism, historical enmity and grievances, imagined injustice and vengeance are seen as a source or a catalyst of a conflict. There are different types of conflicts, but Collier focuses on two types: civil wars and coup d'états. As an economist, he largely disregards politicized causes and considers social and economic preconditions that increase likelihood of a conflict: low income, slow economic growth, dependency on basic commodity exports (Collier, 2007, pp. 17-26). All these factors initially generate an environment of hopelessness when a society seriously considers taking arms and marching to overthrow the government.

Post-Soviet states have popularized a definition such as a frozen conflict. Transnistria, Nagorno-Karabakh, South Ossetia, Abkhazia, the Crimea, Donetsk and Lugansk are all examples of such conflicts, and their common feature that they persist and seem to lack nonviolent solutions. These frozen conflicts are very helpful for Moscow to keep post-Soviet states in its sphere of influence.⁶⁰ Many of these conflicts have recently turned into hot conflicts, and in the case of Nagorno-Karabakh, the gap between perceived strength and real strength of Russia was exposed as Armenia, formally backed by Moscow, has decisively lost. The difference between a frozen conflict and Collier's conflict trap is that the former has a clear ethnic component.

⁶⁰ Lachert, Jacob (March 14, 2019): Post-Soviet Frozen Conflicts: A Challenge for European Security. Warsaw Institute, <https://warsawinstitute.org/post-soviet-frozen-conflicts-challenge-european-security/>, retrieved November 2, 2022.

There is a positive correlation between democracy and peace as demonstrated on the Figure 6 below. The ideal position on the diagram is the upper left quadrant where both democracy and peace are high. Five Central Asian states are marked on the graph relative to other 155 states represented in the calculation. Although CA maintains a relative peace, democracy is considerably below the average level. In order to fully grasp the findings of a short quantitative analysis, the most extreme countries should be examined. Iceland is the most peaceful country located in the upper left area, and Afghanistan is on the other end of the spectrum. As for democracy, Norway is leading as the most democratic country, and it is again Afghanistan as the least democratic state in the world. The trendline is drawn excluding these extreme representations from the equation. The findings presented in the Figure 6 symbolize the very core of the Western advocacy for peace and democracy. The relationship between peace and democracy is self-explanatory and intuitive, remarkably, five countries on the upper right quadrant with high democracy indexes but less peace also exist; one of them is Israel. Compared to Israel, CA is more peaceful and less democratic. Although democracy-peace relationship is established, the graph below shows that there can be a relatively peaceful state with low democracy inferring that peace is more important and primary than democracy. Peace is an integral part of democracy, but democracy is not a founding part of peace. Negative peace, that is absence of violence and open conflict, has always been featured in Central Asian politics and used interchangeably with stability. Especially during the conflict in Tajikistan of early 1990's, people were predominantly inclined to support a leader, who promised negative peace (stability), and consciously gave away their right to build a more inclusive and democratic peace (Barnes & Abdullaev, 2001, p. 10). Central Asian society considers stability as sufficient and the most prioritized objective of the government. People in CA practically tolerate deprivation of their political and social rights as long as the state can ensure there is no open conflict with casualties. However, this trend is changing as there are more protests in even relatively stable Kazakhstan. The 2011 violent clash between oil company workers and police in Zhanaozen is very indicative; the protesters demanded higher wages and better working conditions.⁶¹

⁶¹ Sindelar, Daisy – Toiken, Saniash (December 16, 2012): A Year After Deadly Riots, Zhanaozen Is Quiet But Angry. Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty, <https://www.rferl.org/a/zhanaozen-a-year-after-the-riots/24798726.html>, retrieved March 17, 2023.

Figure 6: Democracy and Peace

Source: *own analysis, data source: (1) Economist Intelligence Unit (2022). Democracy Index 2021**. Economist Intelligence Unit, <https://pages.eiu.com/rs/753-RIQ-438/images/eiu-democracy-index-2021.pdf>, retrieved December 23, 2022. (2) Institute for Economics and Peace (2022). Global Peace Index 2021***. Vision of Humanity, <https://www.visionofhumanity.org/maps/#/>, retrieved Dec 23, 2022.
 *The analysis involves calculation of data on 160 states and visualization of results on a graph with exponential trendline
 **Y-axis - The higher the score the more democratic the country (Ex. 0 is authoritarian, 10 is full democracy)
 ***X-axis - The lower the score the more peaceful the country (Ex. 1 is more peaceful, 4 is less peaceful)

Going from the ideas to specific cases, Central Asia also conceals a few high-risk zones that are less known on the international arena: Karakalpakstan in Uzbekistan, GBAO in Tajikistan, Northern part of Kazakhstan with considerable Russian population and enclaves in Kyrgyzstan are very unstable territories where a hot conflict can easily erupt anytime and have actually sparked several times since the Soviet Union dissolution. Interestingly, geographic characteristics also matter; a country with dispersed population or mountainous terrain is more prone to conflicts (Ibid, p. 26). Especially Karakalpakstan and GBAO are descriptive of Collier’s conflict: low income, slow economic growth and dependency on commodity exports in the environment of appalling poverty.

The conflict trap can be solved by reaching a negative peace and then enhancing sustainable security. Collier warns that even after gaining peace, there are high chances of a state falling back to conflict. Therefore, separating conflicting parties is not sufficient in the long-run perspective. The three problems – low income, slow growth and dependency on basic product exports should be fixed, and that poses a more difficult challenge for both a

government and international actors. Even when a conflict is prevented, hopelessness in the society still persists. For instance, GBAO is a very depressing region where unemployment and underdevelopment force people to engage in narcotrafficking and join rebel groups.

2.2.2 *Landlocked with bad neighbors*

Whole Central Asia is a huge landlocked region, but one country stands out from the rest – Uzbekistan is a doubly-landlocked state. A geographic location as a development challenge traditionally comes as a secondary topic for analysis after such primary ones as economy and institutions. When developed landlocked countries are added into the picture, this strongly dilutes a conclusion since European landlocked states have been demonstrating sustainable growth and development. This falsely suggests that development is not dependent on geography. However, besides Collier, other experts such as Anwarul Chowdhury and Sandagdorj Erdenebileg (2006) emphasize crippling effect of landlocked geography on development outside Europe. They could confirm that there is a strong relationship, and the findings are not so optimistic for such countries.

First, the leaders in economic growth among developing countries are those, which could build export-oriented industries and harness trade. Access to the sea opens up significant opportunities for growth in terms of reaching lucrative markets. Cheap labor and low transportation costs only stimulate production making exports more attractive. Therefore, it is natural for coastal countries to benefit from trade. The reality of landlocked countries is quite the opposite with transportation costs and infrastructure. Chowdhury & Erdenebileg (2006) also include limited choice of trading partners, expensive intermediate goods and infrastructure deficiencies that constrain trade and suppressively make landlocked countries' exports less competitive on the global market.

Landlocked geography practically makes a country vitally dependent on its neighbors and this is the second part of the trap. The problem is not there if the neighboring countries are developed and rich. This makes it easier for a landlocked country to develop by simply cooperating and trading regionally. Even more positive trend is a growth spill over, which suggests that growth of 1% of a neighbor transfers into 0,4% of domestic growth (Ibid, p. 56-58). However, it is a completely different picture for Central Asia. Resource-rich countries are not interested in trading regionally since their main item of export is basic commodities which are transported to bigger markets. Resource-scarce countries are poor and often hostile to each other. The violent border conflict in April 2021 between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan escalated not only from the dispute over undemarcated borders but also from water and land issues (Arynova & Schmeier, 2021). Agricultural and pasture lands are

extremely important for a living in these countries, and they are interdependent on each other. The neighboring communities depend on each others' sources of water but none invests in the modernization of obsolete shared Soviet water infrastructure facilities which only exacerbates the tensions. The second significant Kyrgyz-Tajik conflict in September 2022 included more heavy military equipment and became more geopolitical.⁶² Two countries are also neighbors of Uzbekistan which is the most populous and doubly-landlocked country. Two conflicting states are physically separating Uzbekistan and China, thus, the Kyrgyz-Tajik clashes negatively affect development of Uzbekistan.

Central Asia's landlocked geography inhibit development by disentangling the region from global trade. High transportation cost and lack of access to the sea force the five states to cooperate with each other, but the level of trust and propensity for integration in CA is extremely low. Five states are not motivated to set up a mutually beneficial plan on regional development let alone implement it accordingly. Being landlocked and surrounded with bad neighbors pose a serious challenge. However, the solutions such as trade facilitation, regional integration and much needed investments will be successful only if promoted and commanded by an actor from outside of the region.

2.2.3 *Natural resource trap*

A natural resource trap is a much more complicated type. Rationally, natural resources are certainly an advantage and can be used as a development booster. But in reality, only few countries in the world with abundant natural resources have managed to utilize their advantage. The main argument of Collier is that these resources discourage normal economic activity because of all the rent coming from those resources. It is important to introduce economic definition of 'rent' – excess of revenue that a state receives without additional economic effort. Such unearned revenue often occurs in oil or gas rich countries. For instance, when a price of oil increases, a state earns more by selling the same amount of oil. Thus, oil rich countries' revenues are highly dependent on oil demand and price. The rent itself is not inherently bad for development; the problem arises when a state decides to use that 'extra' revenue for present consumption or embezzlement rather than for investment. In such way, the state borrows wealth for the often unnecessary or even extravagant needs of a current population from future generations.

⁶² Urciuolo, Luca (September 29, 2022): Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan: causes and analysis of an endless border dispute. SpecialEurasia, <https://www.specialeurasia.com/2022/09/29/kyrgyzstan-tajikistan-borders/>, retrieved February 23, 2023.

Figure 7: Resource rents as a % of GDP

Source: own editing, data source: (The World Bank), Total natural resource rents (% of GDP) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.TOTL.RT.ZS>, retrieved on February 22, 2023.

Another problem with such countries is that they are prone to become authoritarian. Democracy declines as the resource rent rises; this tendency is observed almost in all resource rich countries. On average, when the level of rent reaches 8% of national income, democracy is outperformed by autocracy (Ibid, p. 43). Referring to the actual data in the figure above, only Tajikistan fluctuates between 5-6%, and other four countries top over 10%. Autocracy always brings further challenges that thwart state development: poor transparency and isolationism. When there are no internal checks and balances, and external pressure for reforms, it is a favorable environment for corrupt rulers to embezzle state wealth with impunity. Developing countries vitally depend on external assistance, but the problem with resource rich developing countries is that their rulers often reject assistance if it also comes with pressure from external actors for transparency and reforms. The main source of corruption in poor countries is often external assistance, for example, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan; but corruption in resource rich countries is based on embezzlement of resource revenues and rents. Therefore, when UN organizations report that Turkmenistan is an upper-middle income country based on the data provided by authoritarian government, the reliability and accuracy of that report is extremely low.⁶³ Consequently, the Human Development Index (HDI) report, which is an aggregate estimate of nation's longevity,

⁶³ Human Rights Watch (September 23, 2020): Turkmenistan: Denial, Inaction Worsen Food Crisis. Human Rights Watch, <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/09/23/turkmenistan-denial-inaction-worsen-food-crisis>, retrieved March 18, 2023.

education and income, could also be unreliable by placing Turkmenistan as the second-best performer in Central Asia after Kazakhstan – another resource rich country.⁶⁴

Natural resource trap produces explicit problems such as corruption, autocracy and isolationism, and more implicit challenges such as a Dutch disease. In resource rich countries, economic growth is powered by the revenues and rents from mainly oil and gas, which contradicts classic theories of economic development that emphasize industrialization, modernization and diversification of economy as the engines of growth. In other words, Dutch disease implies that growth in one sector leads to decline in other sectors making it less competitive. Besides, with high market prices on oil and gas, the government is capable of creating a false semblance of stability and prosperity by greatly subsidizing basic social goods and services. All this creates a facade of development, which certainly vanishes when the prices for natural resources drop.

The solutions for natural resource trap exist and they are rationalized by economic calculations. Democratization and institutional reforms allow equal distribution of national income and thorough investment into other economic sectors and industries. International standards and rules, if adopted, could stimulate more transparent and quality FDI. But again, observation of the reality in resource rich countries confirms that economically rational decisions are not favored by the political elite. Relative security and fragile peace in the resource rich countries misrepresent the reality and disguise more pressing issues that these countries face – economic dependency on resource rents, isolationism, resilience to reforms and Dutch disease.

2.2.4 Bad governance in a small country

The most subtle trap is bad governance in a small country. If conflicts and natural resources pose certain challenges that are easily comprehensible, a resource-scarce small country with no apparent conflict seems to be a perfect candidate for swift reforms and development. However, the results of reforms and good governance are gradual and prone to be offset by external shocks such as macroeconomic crises and inflation (Collier, 2007, pp. 64-65). In other words, it is easy to be disappointed with the reforms even before they start bringing results. Central Asia, in contrast to Sub-Saharan Africa, also features a Soviet past with a completely different system. By the mid-1980s, it was obvious that Soviet-type socialism was not sustainable, the reforms were much needed or, maybe, even overdue, but the Soviet institutions were incredibly resistant to systemic changes (Aslund, 2007, pp. 15-20). Thus, a

⁶⁴ Human Development Report Office (n.d.): Human Development Index (HDI). HDI UNDP, <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>, retrieved March 18, 2023.

small post-Soviet country with no significant resources and conflicts still experiences stagnation in development which is caused by bad governance. Conclusively, this is the trap that should be avoided by relatively small countries.

The dissolution of the Soviet Union was time of euphoria in the West; but the dilemma about the future of fifteen emerging states puzzled politicians as well as economists. The most popular scenario was outlined in the Washington Consensus, which emerged as the summary of reforms based on the success of the Latin American macroeconomic stabilization in the 1980s. The main promoted reforms and processes were privatization, liberalization of foreign trade, deregulation of economy, investments in the education, health and other social sectors – these are also the features of capitalist system (Ibid, pp. 31-32). Post-Soviet bloc Central European and Baltic governments viewed these reforms as purely economic necessities, whereas Central Asian parochial and corrupt governments emphasized a political dimension and labeled the reforms as a Western intervention. Nonetheless, Kyrgyzstan was an exception because it chose to adopt the Western economic and political systems and principles. As a matter of fact, those reforms underwent with much enthusiasm as Kyrgyzstan planned to become “Switzerland of the East” (Anderson, 1999, p. 90). As mentioned earlier, these reforms don’t work instantly but take time to have an effect. Such a slow progress only intensified anti-West sentiments in the civil society. Extreme sensitivity of these states to external changes can be indicated in their GDP growth rate decline in 2008-2009 financial crisis and in 2019 due to COVID-19 pandemic. Though, such sensitivity suggests that the international community and powers can actually exert influence on such small states to develop. If a regional power is interested in the political stability and development of a small state at its immediate vicinity, then it can use geopolitical tools to influence.

Figure 8: GDP growth rate (annual %)

Source: own editing, data source: (The World Bank), GDP growth (annual %) <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG>, retrieved on February 25, 2023.

What exactly is good governance and how can it be measured? World Bank project – World Governance Indicators (WGI) – classifies six indicators: Voice and Accountability, Political Stability, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, Control of Corruption. The figure below shows the results of a small analysis for Central Asian states. Kazakhstan has been showing progress in governance, but a steep dip in 2010-2013 is a showcase of how a leader consolidates power. Authoritarian rule and corruption have a negative effect on social conditions, so it is a matter of time when social unrest will erupt. In case of Kazakhstan, the indicative event was the protests of oil company workers in Zhanaozen 2011, which were violently suppressed by the government forces. Kyrgyzstan spoiled its progress in 2004-2005 and in spring 2005 is the year of Tulip Revolution when the president Askar Akayev was overthrown. There was another revolution in 2010 which was more violent, yet the indicators didn't drop but rose because Kyrgyzstan became a parliamentary republic after the 2010 political turmoil. Uzbekistan hit the lowest mark in 2005, and the Andijan massacre is the darkest page in its post-independence history. Definitely, worsening governance indicators can be used to predict an approaching conflict, but WGI scope is much wider and better suited to evaluate the quality of state management.

Figure 9: Good Governance Ranking in CA

Source: own analysis, data source: Kaufmann, Daniel – Kraay, Aart (n.d.): Worldwide Governance Indicators, <http://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/>, retrieved on March 12, 2023.

Collier examines the actors that can initiate changes. He emphasizes the importance of heroes with courage and a size of educated civil society. Radical reforms should be introduced in the short-run, and the progress should be meticulously maintained over long-run. But the leaders in CA are corrupt and selfish while the civil society is prone to populism. For instance, second president of Kyrgyzstan – Kurmanbek Bakiyev – tried to negotiate more lucrative deal with the US over the Manas Base near Bishkek, but in 2009 Russia offered a better deal with a condition to evict the US troops in exchange for financial assistance in cash and investments (Cooley, 2012, p. 124). What is more descriptive of greed and corruptness of president Bakiyev is when his son tried to negotiate even better deal with the US after the parliamentary voting on the American base eviction from Kyrgyzstan. The base was portrayed as a threat to regional security and Kyrgyz-Russian relations, so the civil society was manipulated to condemn the presence of the US troops. The character quality and intentions of a leader practically define the politics in the small developing country. Interestingly, good governance and good government principles coincides in the role of the government – both of them state that efficient service of the public must be a priority. Good government principles strongly believe that efficient service can be achieved if a strong and efficient government is in place (Stumpf, 2009, pp. 412-413). On the other hand, Collier (2007, pp. 64-65) doubts that neither the most honest and competent public officials nor the best policies can significantly develop a state if there are no opportunities. In the context of

Central Asia, it is important to note that local leaders do not have motivation to change if it leads to jeopardization of their corruption schemes.

Chapter conclusion

Four traps of Collier have prevented many countries from undertaking healthy and sustainable development. Conflicts such as civil wars and coups can be traced down as a consequence of low income, slow growth and underdevelopment of export. Natural resources in corrupt states only exacerbate the process of development. Greed and corruptness of political elites turn a resource blessing to resource curse. Geography matters a lot if it is the main obstacle between a country and a global trade. A landlocked state is limited to trade with its neighbors because transportation costs and high trade tariffs deprive that state of a competitive advantage. Finally, bad governance in a small country stagnates development. For a country with functioning state institutions, reforms and changes are natural. But a small developing country usually has a corrupt government, which is not interested in changes. Even when a small country undertakes steps towards development, they are easily offset by external shocks or regional powers.

This chapter has had an objective to introduce the geopolitical tools and development traps in order to set a model to analyze the impact of geopolitics on development. These tools and traps are described by Collier, this chapter simply extends his analysis to Central Asian context. Economic background and Western perspective of Collier shapes his analysis as he interprets external interventions as instruments aiming at development. However, Central Asian context features regional powers that largely employ their own perspectives and interests. These powers effectively turn those instruments into geopolitical tools. The next chapter examines four cases in Central Asia, which specifically demonstrate how geopolitics impacts development.

3 CHAPTER: CASE STUDIES

Collier is positive that developing countries should be assisted by the international community. He relies on the collective actions of the Group of Eight (G8). This group consisted of France, Germany, Italy, the UK, Japan, the US, Canada, and Russia in 2007 when Collier's book was published. This suggests that Collier supports the engagement of powerful states in the development process. However, Collier's main focus on the G8 might be explained by his economic field of expertise; if he was more inclined to political field, he might have focused on the UN Security Council. The G8 receives a lot of criticism, probably, the most argumentative point is that the group doesn't represent a truly international

composition. The G8 in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa could be relevant, but in the context of Central Asia, there are different actors and different geopolitical interests. Another significant factor is the political culture of the region, which is intimately defined by its Soviet heritage. The CA states have been ruled by former communists, and some of them are still instinctively loyal to Moscow. Personalities of the first leaders after the wave of independence have been fundamental. John Anderson (1999, p. 42) have eloquently summarized that:

"Following the collapse of the Soviet Union many of the successor states, lacking any experience of self-government let alone democratic politics, have found the shape of their new politics very much determined by the character and style of the leader in power at the time independence was gained."

Four cases below are examined in order to find how geopolitics impacts development in Central Asia.

3.1 Conflict in Tajikistan

The conflict trap is the most obvious because it clearly exacerbates conditions for development. The main preconditions of a civil war, according to Collier, are low income, slow growth and dependence upon primary commodity exports. Mountainous terrain also affects negatively and increases chances of a conflict. Nevertheless, nationalism and religious discrimination also play crucial role in the conflict eruptions. Political culture and motives of political leaders, quite often dictated by their perception of personal security and mercantile interests, define scenario and destiny of a state. Geopolitics, in terms of regional powers, neighboring states and actors, influence domestic politics by using geopolitical tools.

Tajikistan was traditionally the poorest and the least developed state in the Soviet Union. Besides poor social and economic conditions, the Tajiks were clearly underrepresented in politics, although they were more than half of the population; communist party membership was traditionally dominated by the Russians holding around 40% of membership while around 13% of population (Hiro, 2011, p. 299). With over 90% of its territory as mountainous, geography has played important role in defragmentation of people into urban versus rural, industrial versus agricultural, cosmopolitan versus traditional. Tajiks owe to the Soviet Union for its emergence as a distinct nation with an internationally recognized state, on the other hand, it was the Soviets who renamed them and separated from a bigger 'Persian' world. Tajiks have always been aware that other four Central Asian countries are ethnically Turkic. During the Soviet Era, Turkification of the Tajiks took place in order to

eliminate perceived threat because the Tajiks were considered to be more religious and less loyal (Foltz, 2019, p. 119). Especially frosty relations are between Tajikistan and Uzbekistan. Both countries have a considerable minority of each other's ethnicities; about 25% of the population in Tajikistan are Uzbeks (Barnes & Abdullaev, 2001, p. 18). Another thorn is historical grievances over the 'loss' of Persian cities of Bukhara and Samarkand to Uzbeks, causing ethnical animosity between the two nations. Such a mix of different aspects presumed a big potential for a conflict. These tensions within Tajikistan were suppressed by the Soviet rule. But currently, the tensions arise over the topic of water management – Uzbeks need it for its agriculture and Tajiks aspire to build a hydroelectric dam. Therefore, conflict eruption could easily be predicted as soon as the Soviet Union collapsed, and all these factors have played crucial geopolitical roles in the post-Soviet history of Tajikistan. After gaining independence from the Soviet Union on 9th September 1991, the Tajiks had their first presidential elections in November. Those were truly multi-party elections with the participation of the Communists, Islamic Revival Party (IRPT), Democratic Party (DPT) and Ruby of Badakhshan (Foltz, 2019, p. 149). The non-Communist parties were in some part inspired by the radical political changes in Afghanistan and Iran; glasnost and perestroika reforms only boosted political changes. The wave of changes was overwhelming and affecting the dormant Tajik identity – the statue of Lenin in Dushanbe was replaced with a statue of the Persian poet Firdausi, who flipped the concept of Turan into anti-Turk and anti-Arab term, while glorifying the Persian identity. However, since the Soviet rule had still been very strong in Tajikistan's urbanized regions; the victory of a communist candidate had been predictable. This generated resentment among the opposition, and led to the alliance of IRPT and democrats. In the spring of 1992, protestors flooded into Dushanbe from the regions; the people were mainly mobilized by the IRPT. The unrest spread and the government lost control over the capital to the opposition forces. In November 1992, Emomali Rahmonov, the former kolkhoz director, was elected by the Supreme Soviet as the effective head of state. With military support from Uzbekistan and Russia, Rahmonov regained the capital in December 1992. Instead of reconciliation, massive persecutions followed forcing the opposition to flee to GBAO and neighboring Afghanistan. The IRPT rebranded itself as the United Tajik Opposition (UTO). In April 1994, UN peace talks, initiated by Russia, Iran and Pakistan started and Rahmonov was forced to ease his rule and conduct presidential elections in November, that he won allegedly by falsifications and fraud (Hiro, 2011, pp. 329-330). The active stage of the civil war formally ended when Rahmonov and the UTO leader met in Bishkek on May 17, 1997 to sign a peace agreement (Ibid, p.

331). The hot stage of the civil war left Tajikistan devastated. According to some estimates, up to 100,000 dead and approximately 500,000 internally displaced, economy in shatters (Foltz, 2019, p. 153). On the other hand, the peace agreement envisioned democratic structure of the country by legitimizing the opposition and allocating 30% quota to the UTO in the political structure, but the conditions were vague and complicated (Goryayev, 2001, p. 37). Those conditions were ignored, thus, leaving the opposition without political leverage and fair representation.

Rahmonov started the process of power consolidation and manipulation with national identity by amending the constitution and reviving pre-Islamic history of the Tajiks, for example, he omitted Slavic ending of his surname and became Emomali Rahmon. Still, he was the most preferred figure by Moscow for stability and loyalty. Russia promised to assist Tajikistan in economic and military aspects in order to help Rahmon stay in power (Hiro, 2011, p. 338). It was vital for his political security since more than half of the Tajiks live in Afghanistan, Uzbekistan; working migrants in Russia also round up to about one million Tajiks (Foltz, 2019, pp. 173-174). Diasporas can be a formidable political opposition or a financial source to continue a conflict (Collier, 2007, pp. 22-23). Tajiks outside of their homeland, especially in Afghanistan, and in GBAO are perceived as a threat and the likelihood of their cooperation with the Taliban worries Rahmon to these days. GBAO still experiences military raids from Dushanbe which often result in casualties; the recent brutal crackdown took place in spring 2022 in the administrative town of Khorog.⁶⁵

The 9/11 attacks allowed Tajikistan to receive larger attention from the US, and their compatible anti-Taliban stances allowed them to build strategic ties. Tajikistan joined NATO Partnership for Peace (PfP), allowed its airspace and few facilities to be used to combat against the Taliban; in return, aid and assistance flowed in the country (Hiro, 2011, pp. 335-336).

China sees Tajikistan's importance predominantly in regional security matters. Although trade deficit, foreign debt accumulation and even land concessions feature this unequal relationship, military cooperation against Islamist threat including the Taliban and Uighur separatists is central.⁶⁶ It is dubious if Tajikistan can effectively benefit from the BRI

⁶⁵ RFERL Tajik Service (June 22, 2022): Fear and Outrage in Pamir: Tajikistan's Gorno-Badakhshan Reeling from Brutal State Crackdown. Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty, <https://www.rferl.org/a/tajikistan-gorno-badakhshan-brutal-crackdown/31910506.html>, retrieved March 2, 2023.

⁶⁶ Schulz, Dante (March 4, 2022): China-Tajikistan Bilateral Relations. Caspian Policy Center, <https://www.caspianpolicy.org/research/security-and-politics-program-spp/china-tajikistan-bilateral-relations>, retrieved March 2, 2023.

because, despite having borders with China, its geography poses an extreme challenge. High mountain ranges are still a problem for transportation and communication; even the civil war subsided during winter seasons. Whereas nonarable lands of GBAO make it virtually dependent on the assistance from Dushanbe or foreign donors for more than half of its needs (Grogan, 2021, p. 4).

The prospects of development are bleak in Tajikistan. The construction of Rogun hydroelectric dam is the paramount Tajik hope but it is constantly delayed or restrained by Uzbekistan since the dam will negatively affect Uzbek agricultural sector (Foltz, 2019, p. 161). There is also a geopolitical reason – such a massive dam will allow Tajikistan to become an important regional player by exporting electricity (Jacoby, 2017, p. 125). Recently, Rogun has elevated from regional geopolitical object to global geopolitics as the EU has shown interest in investing in the construction in order to minimize Russian influence on Tajikistan and respond symmetrically to the Chinese BRI expansion.⁶⁷

Sub-chapter conclusion

Uzbek and Russian military interventions and assistance helped to bring a negative peace but at the same time allowed an authoritarian leader to capture power, which has undermined democratic development of Tajikistan. Elimination of the Islamist emergence in Tajikistan and protection of the Uzbeks were the main motives of Uzbekistan for its decision to intervene militarily (Hiro, 2011, pp. 320-321). Yeltsin was more concerned with the political consequences in Russia if he hadn't been able to show that he couldn't protect around 300,000 ethnic Russians in Tajikistan, so a negative peace with a loyal president was a preferable scenario (Ibid, pp. 319-320). With the main objective to tackle the Taliban in Afghanistan, the US military assistance, aid, and NATO PfP agreement virtually legitimized an authoritarian power of Rahmon in the eyes of the West. Iran's recent hybrid assistance in the form of a drone factory and its desire to cooperate with Tajikistan in order to keep a partner against the Taliban damages regional security. The UN peacebuilding role, due to insufficient understanding of the conflict, structured an inefficient mechanism that Rahmon could easily exploit at his own advantage. The OSCE condemned corrupt elections and undemocratic amendments, but this failed to have any effect (Ibid, pp. 337-338). Chinese military assistance further strengthens the power of Rahmon by allowing him to modernize its security forces which he uses against GBAO and Kyrgyzstan. Trade facilitation with

⁶⁷ Guarascio, Francesco – Pirnazarov, Nazarali (July 6, 2022): EU plans investment in world's tallest dam to dent Russia's energy clout. Reuters, <https://www.reuters.com/article/ukraine-crisis-eu-tajikistan-idAFL8N2YM2FR,retrieved>, retrieved March 17, 2023.

China doesn't present a viable path to development due to challenging geography and availability of alternatives with other Central Asian states, namely Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. Tajikistan as a buffer zone works well for China since it proved cheap to keep the state through CSO mechanisms and partially take the war on terrorism out of its mainland to a neighboring country. Aga Khan Foundation assistance to GBAO has a positive effect, but it is curbed by the government since there is a suspicion that the Foundation has a fundamental geopolitical goal to unite Pamiri people and transform GBAO into the first Ismaili Shia state. External interventions have demonstrated inability to help Tajikistan free from the conflict trap in the long run. The reasons are the characteristics of Tajikistan's political culture such as authoritarian regime, corruption, clientelism, Soviet-style mode of rule and regime survival. All the external actors, except Aga Khan foundation, have been tolerating and cooperating with the authoritarian regime. Rough geographic conditions have also negatively affected development. Convincingly, in a conflict trap, external intervention can damage long-term prospects of the state development if the main objective is limited to a negative peace. The preconditions of a conflict are still persistent: low income, slow growth and underdeveloped export sector. As a result, the conflicts still erupt in Tajikistan as it keeps raiding GBAO and neighboring Kyrgyzstan. Geopolitics negatively impact development in the situation of a conflict if the geopolitical actors tolerate predatory local political culture and lack genuine interest in resolving the conflict in favor of the most affected parties. In other words, it is not a negative impact of geopolitics per se, but skillful marginal tactics of local rulers that spoil positive effect on development. Unsurprisingly, a victorious corrupt dictator Rahmon made himself a president for life and amended the constitution for smooth transfer of power to his son through a rigged referendum in May 2016, practically pushing Tajikistan closer to a family-run failed state.⁶⁸

3.2 Double-landlocked Uzbekistan

Every Central Asian state is landlocked but Uzbekistan stands out as a doubly-landlocked country that borders with all the rest plus Afghanistan. Such a restricting geography makes it dependent on its neighbors and greatly reduces its scope in trade. This would be even more serious factor if a country was economically weak and politically unstable. But the case of Uzbekistan becomes even more interesting since it is the most populous in the region, resource rich and industrialized. Collier also mentions that 'bad neighbors' exacerbate

⁶⁸ Standish, Reid (May 25, 2016): How Tajikistan's President Extended his Term—for Life. Foreign Policy Magazine, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2016/05/25/how-tajikistans-president-extended-his-term-for-life-rahmon-isis-migrant-imf/>, retrieved March 10, 2023.

already inhibiting geographic challenge. In case of Uzbekistan, the relationships with Tajikistan and Afghanistan are not friendly, complicated with Kyrgyzstan and passive with Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan. All these challenges hamper development, and authoritarian regime has been constantly emphasizing security issues effectively equating state survival and regime survival. Relations with Afghanistan and Tajikistan, worsened at the demise of the Soviet Union. On the other hand, Uzbekistan's geographic location makes a perfect starting point for regional economic integration, which is vitally important for development of a landlocked state according to Collier.

During late Soviet period, Uzbekistan was preoccupied with growing popularity of Islam and nationalism. A big bulk of the Soviet ground forces entered Afghanistan in 1979 through the Termez bridge over the river Amu Darya because it was the only bridge capable of holding heavy military vehicles. In response, the US increased its military assistance to Afghanistan and spread anti-Soviet propaganda through Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty (RFERL) in Soviet Muslim states; the US allies from the Middle East also transmitted courses on Quran (Hiro, 2011, p. 124). Optimistic Gorbachev's glasnost and perestroika also contributed to religious and national liberalization. Uzbek society was willing to revise its attitude to Islam, which was stigmatized as backward and toxic by Moscow. Pan-Turkism and Uzbek language were also gaining sympathizers. Obviously, the Communists felt threatened, but Islam Karimov (1938-2016) – a newly appointed Soviet leader of Uzbekistan – decided to support and capitalize on these movements to win the 1990 Communist Party Elections (Ibid, pp. 131-135). The preconditions for conflict were clearly forming among people but unlike Tajikistan, Uzbekistan averted from falling into a civil war.

Karimov managed to stay in power after the SU dissolution. He was quick to make an unbelievable rebranding of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan to People's Democratic Party (PDP) in 1991. Karimov's desire to build relations with the West, predominantly the US, and receive membership in the IMF and OSCE made him pretend to be a moderate ruler with tolerance towards opposition. The US conditions for launching bilateral diplomatic relations were traditional: acceptance of all US-Soviet Union agreements, respect for human rights, free market, democratic elections and a true multiparty political system. He promised to conduct reforms but that was a bluff. As soon as the US embassy opened in Tashkent in 1992, Karimov unleashed brutal crackdown on the opposition. In the same year, Uzbekistan proposed to sign a Tashkent Collective Security Agreement during the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) meeting. This historical agreement served as the origin of the CSTO later when Uzbekistan left the agreement.

Karimov kept his course on rapprochement with the West, and the US was especially pleased. His war on terror was in unison with the US Global War on Terrorism (GWOT) as the Uzbek security forces kept cracking on Hizb-Ut-Tahrir, Wahabis and the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU). The war on terror backfired politically as Karimov's harsh actions and worsening economic situation gave more incentives for Uzbeks to join these movements and, eventually, making them more politicized as an opposition (Khanna, 2008, pp. 110-111). Islamist threat and terrorism were the issues where Tashkent and Washington cooperated. Military assistance and cooperation during the years of Clinton presidency resulted in the trainings of Uzbek troops by the US and joint forces that periodically entered Afghanistan with an objective to eliminate Usama bin Laden (Hiro, 2011, pp. 158-159). In 2001, the foundation of the Karshi-Khanabad (K2) US military base signaled a major geopolitical shift in Central Asia. Surely, American bases always come with benefits in terms of aid and assistance, which often allure autocratic leaders to cooperate with the US. Especially financial aid meant for economic development is spent to pay salaries of loyal security forces in the authoritarian state. But even more important benefit is that the US regularly refrains from criticizing domestic politics of the host country and even secretly assists it in fighting against political opposition. For instance, CIA kept transporting suspects to Uzbekistan, although the State Department was completely aware of this and criticized for cooperating with a country known for horrible human rights violations. As Khanna (2008, p. 113) notes:

“If America continues to focus only on relations with regimes—in contrast to Europe's focus on improving systems—then even Karimov's successors may simply continue the practice of currying favor with China and Russia. As one former Uzbek official accusingly remarked at a quiet restaurant in Tashkent, “Western strategy should change from labeling a leader ‘our son of a bitch’ to just a plain ‘son of a bitch.’”

Indeed, European organizations were more critical of human rights matters in Uzbekistan. When Karimov prepared a pompous annual general meeting of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) in 2003, the speeches of EBRD were extremely disparaging. The meeting was broadcasted live and Karimov experienced his, probably, worst moment of humiliation (Hiro, 2011, pp. 176-177). He imagined this moment to be historic for Uzbekistan's ascendance to the international arena as a significant player, but it turned out to be his realization that the West is not well used to flirting with his authoritarian

regime. Besides, the West has broken an unwritten rule of the Oriental and subtle political culture to praise a host, not criticize him – East is a delicate matter.

The end to the US-Uzbek active but controversial cooperation came aftermath the Andijan massacre in May 2005, when the West criticized the Uzbek government for violence in suppressing the protest and imposed sanctions in terms of blacklisting a few Uzbek officials. The State Department under pressure from human rights organizations decided to conduct investigation. The Uzbek refugees from Andijan in Kyrgyzstan were planned to be relocated to Romania in the UN proposal rather than turning them in to Uzbekistan and that was the last straw as the Uzbek government sent a message to the US embassy informing about the termination of K2 military base (Cooley, 2012, p. 39). The UN proposal implied assistance but not to the Uzbek government and, therefore, it managed to save around five hundred refugees from the authoritarian regime by relocating them.

In case of relationship with Tajikistan and Afghanistan, Uzbekistan can be analyzed as an actor due to significant ethnic Uzbek population in those countries and Uzbekistan's strong military capacity. The Taliban in Afghanistan has been considered a threat since its emergence. Turkmens kept neutrality against the Taliban and Tajiks were not capable of forming a capable military resistance. Karimov, on the other hand, had a close ally – General Abdul Rashid Dostum – an ethnic Uzbek with a stronghold in Afghan Mazar-e Sharif. Uzbekistan, the US and Iran supplied him since he fought against Taliban expansion. Even after eventual retreat and flight of Dostum, Uzbekistan has remained an important channel of assistance to Afghanistan and the US gradually eases its restrictions on Uzbekistan in order to cooperate on Afghan factor. The relations with Tajikistan are strained due to two matters: minorities of each other's ethnicities in the two countries and water issues. Uzbek Samarkand and Bukhara are contested by Tajiks, while Tajik Khujand and its surroundings are a home to sizable Uzbek minority. Uzbekistan closed many Tajik schools and repressed Tajik identity. This repression took place during the Soviet Era as well, and Tajiks registered themselves as Uzbeks out of fear (Hiro, 2011, pp. 171-175). To some extent, forced Uzbekization of Tajiks is a controversial policy by Karimov whose father was an ethnic Tajik according to his own words. Water issue is a truly post-Soviet dispute with roots in the Soviet Era. According to a primitive regulation, upstream countries of Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan would provide water for agriculture of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan in summer and receive oil and gas in return during winter season. Post-Soviet times opened new markets for hydrocarbons, but poor upstream countries were at disadvantage since it is impossible to change the direction of rivers. Building dams to harness hydroelectric potential is an

opportunity for development, but then downstream countries receive less for their agriculture, especially cotton. With modernized irrigation systems of Uzbekistan, hydroelectric dams wouldn't pose a challenge, but the country keeps exploiting Soviet-type infrastructure with enormous water loss. Each attempt of Tajikistan to build a huge Rogun dam is always opposed by Uzbekistan during UN or WB-organized meetings and blocking equipment delivery through Uzbekistan if it is suspected to be used for the dam construction (Jacoby, 2017). It is a vicious circle when lack of modernization and development lead to geopolitical confrontation with a neighbor and that confrontation inhibits development.

Relationship with China started warming up with the demise of relations with the West in 2003. Uzbekistan doesn't border with China and has highly protectionist trade policy. However, Turkmen gas must pass through Uzbekistan (and then Kazakhstan) to reach China, therefore, making the two countries favor cooperation. Post-Andijan reorientation to the east can be clearly observed as the 2005 trade volume of 628 US millions increased to 3,288 million in 2012 (Paramonov, 2017). A route through Kyrgyzstan is the shortest and essential for densely populated Ferghana valley mainly occupied and inhabited by Uzbeks (Peyrouse, 2007, pp. 26-27). Thus, trade relations between Uzbekistan and China have a positive spillover on regional development. Uzbekistan joined the CSO in 2001 and since then positions as an integral part of the organization in countering Islamist and terrorist threat from Afghanistan. The Regional Anti-Terrorism Structure (RATS) has been established with its headquarters in Tashkent (Cooley, 2012, p. 78). Karimov certainly liked Chinese approach with emphasis on non-interference in domestic affairs in contrast to the Western constant criticism of lack of progress in democratization and human rights violations.

Controversial Karimov died in 2016. The rule of an authoritarian regime is to abolish legacy of a former leader by a new regime. Shavkat Mirziyoyev – has ascended to power and he has been more active in engaging Uzbekistan with other international actors. In 2019, The Economist selected Uzbekistan as the country of the year for its reforms and progress in democratization and abolishing forced labor.⁶⁹ The war in Ukraine even further distanced Uzbekistan from Russia and moved it closer to China and Turkey. The Chinese SCO summit was held in Samarkand in September 2022, which featured the start of the accession

⁶⁹ The Economist (December 21, 2019): Which nation improved the most in 2019? The Economist, <https://www.economist.com/leaders/2019/12/21/which-nation-improved-the-most-in-2019>, retrieved March 7, 2023.

procedure for Iran and increasing attention to security issues related to Afghanistan.⁷⁰ Uzbekistan joined the OTS in 2018 and hosted the summit in Samarkand in November, where Turan Special Economic Zone was announced.⁷¹ Both summits symbolize fundamental geopolitical movements in the region and beyond with Uzbekistan finally realizing its potential to become a true regional power.

Sub-chapter conclusion

Uzbekistan has always possessed a special geopolitical status as a regional power. The country has internal resources for development; however, its special geography and ‘bad’ neighbors have been posing great challenge. Moreover, regional powers have demonstrated different policies towards Uzbekistan. Early engagement with the West in terms of cooperating in security and economy had limited positive impact on development. As an important regional ally of the US in GWOT, Uzbekistan received military assistance and economic benefits. The Pentagon and CIA even assisted Uzbek security forces in cracking on political opposition. Such tolerance from the US only further legitimized and strengthened authoritarian regime, and aid had been used to cover security costs such as salaries rather than stimulate development. In contrast to the Pentagon and CIA approach, the State Department took side of human rights organizations, which eventually led to deterioration of bilateral relations. China’s obsession with regional security has also assisted the authoritarian regime. Military assistance and cooperation concerning threat from Afghanistan had been a priority before the BRI. Now China considers Uzbekistan as a market, natural resource provider and a link of the route leading to even bigger markets. This has had a positive effect in terms of increased connectivity. China is now interested not only in security but also in stability of the region to ensure sustainable trade routes and uninterrupted oil and gas supplies to its mainland. Turkey has been delighted to finally gain an important Turkic state as a partner in the OTS framework. Its long-term geopolitical vision of a Pan-Turkic confederation has shifted closer to realization. Uzbekistan is an integral component to the Chinese solution of the Afghan question. After the retreat of the US from Afghanistan and Russian growing impotence, it is actually China, Uzbekistan and Iran that could cooperate to solve this geopolitical cobweb through SCO framework.

⁷⁰ Muratbekova, Albina (n.d.): 2022 SCO Summit in Samarkand: Key Takeaways. Eurasian Research Institute, <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/2022-sco-summit-in-samarkand-key-takeaways/>, retrieved March 7, 2023.

⁷¹ Daniyarova, Aimoor (November 11, 2022): Organization of Turkic States meets in Uzbekistan. Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies, <https://www.ankasam.org/organization-of-turkic-states-meets-in-uzbekistan/?lang=en>, retrieved March 7, 2023.

Noticeably, this parade of substantial geopolitical changes wouldn't have been possible, if the Uzbek leadership had been as isolationist and marginal as Karimov. Post-Karimov Uzbekistan has been making amazing progress and capitalizing on the geopolitical involvement and interest of regional powers. One might consider that geopolitics positively impacts development in Uzbekistan, but the full picture is that it is the domestic political rule and culture that has defined the reach and effectiveness of external geopolitical intervention. Furthermore, political will of the new Uzbek leadership practically diminishes the negative impact of the country's landlocked geography and bad neighbors on development. Interestingly, Uzbekistan's economic progress forces to rethink the Western principle of democracy as necessary for development and closely observe if the so-called Chinese model might successfully materialize in Uzbekistan.⁷²

3.3 Resource curse of Turkmenistan

Natural resource trap is a classic abnormality in the development theory. The main prerequisite for development is a source of finance and some countries are blessed with enormous volumes of gas and oil, but that blessing turns into a curse when autocratic, corrupt regime overtakes state management. Corrupt government fortifies its position by strengthening its security forces and effectively demolishing democratic principles of free and fair elections, free press and basic human rights. Both Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan are unbelievably rich in gas and oil. Small population of these countries would theoretically allow their citizens to completely live off income from natural resources and develop other industries for economy diversification. However, the reality is that Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan are stagnant and their economies are virtually dependent on natural resource revenues and fluctuations on gas and oil prices. Ideally, external powers should strive to help people in those countries to eradicate autocratic regimes, but mercantile objectives win over moral values. Although there are more scholarly works on Kazakhstan, the analysis concentrates on Turkmenistan to popularize the country in the academia and encourage further studies.

The former communist leader – Saparmurat Niyazov – managed to hold power and become the first president after independence. He renamed the Communist party to Democratic Party and continued to rule. Turkmenistan was not fortunate with its leader as he proved to be a short-sighted politician with no firm understanding of economics and geopolitics. Besides,

⁷² Hedlund, Stefan (August 24, 2022): Uzbekistan's bumpy ride out of Russia's orbit. Geopolitical Intelligence Services, <https://www.gisreportsonline.com/r/uzbekistan-russia-relations/>, retrieved March 7, 2023.

Niyazov had an extremely megalomaniac personality with surreal ideas that he turned into ridiculous domestic policies. The inclusion of his book *Ruhnama* in the curriculum, underfunding of education and healthcare systems only contributed to degradation of a civil society (Bohr, 2016, pp. 42-47). Initially, Turkmenians had free gas, electricity and water since the state could afford providing these social goods due to massive gas revenues (Hiro, 2011, p. 198). But as discussed earlier, this is a clear symptom of a Dutch disease when gas revenues discourage development of other sectors. Russia, until Chinese takeover in 2009-2011, managed the exports of Turkmen gas, but did not address the Dutch disease problems because Russia itself suffers from these problems. Certainly, there is also a ‘rentier effect’ of the resource rich country – low taxes and subsidized social goods discourage resistance to authoritarian regime and accountability from the government (Bohr, 2016, p. 16). Collier also notices the absence of checks and balances in resource rich countries. Another aspect that makes Turkmenistan unique in geopolitics is its neutrality officially recognized by the UN resolution on December 12, 1995.⁷³ The most important implication of such status is that the country avoids joining/hosting military/security organizations and participate in economic blockades. Neutrality is also stated in the constitution. This could be the main reason why Turkmenistan abstains from voting in the recent UN resolutions related to the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

Turkmenistan was the first CA state to sign NATO PfP agreement with the US in 1994. Niyazov allowed the use of the Turkmen air space for the US planes heading to Afghanistan and K2 military base in Uzbekistan after the 9/11 attacks (Ibid, pp. 209-210). As usual, the US aid followed. Resource rich authoritarian state didn’t need external assistance, but Niyazov probably wanted to ensure informal US patronage and cover to keep transferring state revenues from gas sales to his personal overseas bank accounts, especially the one in Deutsche Bank. The cooperation was kept secretive as much as possible, but the leaks claim that Turkmenistan also gave permission of emergency use of the Mary 2 Military airbase (Cooley, 2012, p. 43). Moreover, investigations by international organizations revealed and the officials in Washington admitted that some payments for different avia logistics services were made to that exact Deutsche Bank account.⁷⁴ The US was also interested in Turkmen

⁷³ Indeo, Fabio (December 22, 2020): Turkmenistan’s neutrality: rising security problems. NATO Defense College Foundation, <https://www.natofoundation.org/central-asia/turkmenistans-neutrality-rising-security-problems/>, retrieved March 12, 2023.

⁷⁴ Tynan, Deirdre (July 12, 2010): Pentagon Paid Airport Fees to Turkmenistan, But Can’t Say How Much. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/pentagon-paid-airport-fees-to-turkmenistan-but-cant-say-how-much>, retrieved March 12, 2023.

gas, especially in earning from transporting that gas to big markets such as India and Pakistan through Afghanistan, currently more known as Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India (TAPI) gas pipeline. The origins of this project are in 1996 when Niyazov awarded US-affiliated Centgas consortium with the TAPI contract. For such a cooperative spirit, the US officials refrained from criticizing an obviously autocratic regime with cult personality. As anywhere else in CA, the US has repeatedly proven that it can actually tolerate a totalitarian regime and even cooperate with it. Niyazov, on the other hand, proved that Turkmen neutrality can easily be violated for political and economic benefits.

Post-independent foreign affairs of Turkmenistan prioritized Russia as its strategic partner. Two central aspects that defined the relationship were gas and ethnic Russians in Turkmenistan. Gas exports completely depended on the Russian pipelines and management. Enormous gas volumes were bought at a fraction of a market price and exported through Russian pipelines, thus, barely contributing to the economic growth of Turkmenistan. Ethnic Russians in Turkmenistan had a shaky position when the government made Turkmen language official. Although a slim minority, Russians represented a high-skilled workforce essential for the country to make it through a transition period. In order to guarantee Russian disposition, Turkmenistan signed a ten-year agreement on dual citizenship in 1993. But in 2003, dual citizenship holders, mostly ethnic Russians, faced a draconian requirement to choose only one citizenship. While constantly preaching about defending rights of Russians abroad and mission to reassert in the Eurasian realm, Moscow's weak response was surprising. Interestingly, Gazprom signed a lucrative 25-year gas contract in the same year.⁷⁵ Apparently, Moscow didn't want to spoil a huge step in becoming a primary gas supplier to Europe with a quarrel over a few thousand Russians. Moscow's manipulations with ethnic Russians abroad basically demonstrate that the people are instruments in its geopolitical games.

Neighboring Iran can't be ignored in the Turkmen foreign affairs, but contrary to the assumption that Iran would pose a threat, two countries get along peacefully. Turkey is another important partner that was used to be seen as a model for Central Asian states by the West. Iranian ports at the Persian Gulf are a more attractive access to the sea than Russian closest ports located at the Baltic Sea. This is a huge advantage for trade route diversification. The railway between two countries was opened 1996, Memorandum of Understanding for a

⁷⁵ Kanapiyanova, Zhuldyz (n.d.): Turkmenistan-Russia Energy Cooperation in the Context of Natural Gas Trading. Eurasian Research Institute, <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/turkmenistan-russia-energy-cooperation-in-the-context-of-natural-gas-trading/>, retrieved March 12, 2023.

pipeline between Turkmenistan, Iran and Turkey was signed in 1997 (Hiro, 2011, p. 204). Iran – a state with huge territory and second largest reserves of natural gas – is not homogenous; its northern part actually needs to import gas from Turkmenistan and it had been doing so up until 2017. Turkmenistan switched off the valve due to over one billion US\$ debt of Iran for gas. But two dictatorships engage in diplomatic negotiations instead of escalating into the conflict.

Obviously, Turkey is motivated to gain access to Turkmen gas and weaken Russian and Chinese hegemony. Caspian Sea Legal Status Convention was signed between littoral states in 2018. The agreement should have become a turning point in integration but instead it had a loophole that gives power to Iran and Russia to veto any submarine pipeline construction.⁷⁶ This is a big obstacle for a gas pipeline that is envisaged to travel from Turkmenistan to Turkey via Azerbaijan and Georgia. Turkic ethnicity of Turkey and Turkmenistan played a crucial role for Turkmen education system, which has long been a subject of gravely incompetent management and neglect. Turkmen-Turkish high schools were superior in quality; besides, young people could learn Turkish, Russian and English as well. This was a huge advantage for non-Turkmens since education in state schools was conducted only in Turkmen language. Turkish school graduates were better equipped for career and there were more and more people in the state sector, which concerned the authoritarian regime. Consequently, Gurbanguly Berdimuhamedov regime started closing down these schools.⁷⁷ Turkey has become the top choice destination for political asylum and anyone who wanted to escape poverty and hopelessness in Turkmenistan.

Gurbanguly Berdimuhamedov – a dentist by profession and a minister of Health Ministry during Niyazov – came to power in February 2007 after Niyazov death in December 2006. Contrary to expectations of the international community that the death of the dictator would instigate political turmoil or even a color revolution, the change of power was swift with no protests in the society. Berdimuhamedov proved to be no better than his predecessor, and traditionally started building his own system and getting rid of Niyazov's legacy and network. He also succeeded in placing his son as the president in March 2022. Thus, Turkmenistan has practically become a family business of Berdimuhamedov's dynasty.

⁷⁶ Pannier, Bruce (September 13, 2022): Europe's Wait for Turkmen Natural Gas Continues. Foreign Policy Research Institute, <https://www.fpri.org/article/2022/09/europes-wait-for-turkmen-natural-gas-continues/>, retrieved March 15, 2023.

⁷⁷ Fitzpatrick, Catherine A. (August 22, 2011): Turkmenistan: Turkish Schools Closed Amid Concerns of Spread of Nurchilar Movement. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/turkmenistan-turkish-schools-closed-amid-concerns-of-spread-of-nurchilar-movement>, retrieved March 13, 2023.

Chinese talent to get along with the Central Asian authoritarian regimes is exemplary in Turkmenistan. As it is for other regional players, the main geopolitical incentive for China is gas resources. The Chinese scramble for CA resources technically diversified export destinations for Turkmen gas, but in reality, Turkmenistan has shifted from one monopolist to another without experiencing any positive political or social development. Surely, the exports increased but that revenue didn't transfer into social development. In 2021, Turkmen pipelines supplied 31,5 billion cubic meters of gas to China, the volume increases to 41,7 bcm probably by adding some Uzbek and Kazakh gas; in the same year, Russia supplied 7,6 bcm through pipelines and 6,2 bcm in LNG (BP p.l.c., 2022, p. 47). Turkmenistan has become the biggest external supplier of pipeline gas, unfortunately, the deal was a rip-off because Ashgabat repays for the construction of the pipelines, extraction and transportation costs as well as debt by supplying gas (Bohr, 2016, p. 78). Obviously, Turkmenistan incurs huge losses and remains in a disadvantageous, vassal position in the relationship with China, but Berdimuhamedov's family continues to exploit people and deposit more and more embezzled cash offshore in the Western Banks such as Deutsche Bank.

Sub-chapter conclusion

Unfortunately, the prospects of development in Turkmenistan are vague and dubious. Blessed with the fourth largest reserves of natural gas, Turkmenistan should have been a giant version of Qatar if it exported resources at a real market price and used the revenues to boost internal consumption. If Turkmenistan had managed to invest one half of resource revenues in other industries, education and health sector and the other half in long-term savings, it would have replicated a success story of Norway. Unfortunately, Turkmenistan demonstrates the worst consequences of resource curse – dictatorship, underdevelopment and terrifying human rights violations. Internal factors of swelling resource curse are apolitical civil society and weak national identity as well as rentier effect. Focus on the external factors of natural resource trap allows to identify several regional powers engaged in the scramble for Turkmen gas and, to lesser extent, oil. Even the US has demonstrated that it can betray its conviction to spread democracy to developing countries, when there are massive hydrocarbon resources at stake. Saparmurat Niyazov and then Berdimuhamedov family have been robbing the country and the US has been collaborating with them. Russian prime geopolitical interest hasn't been gas for its own consumption but the opportunity in earning hefty markup by re-exporting it to Europe and any other customers through the Soviet pipelines. Its lack of incentive in modernizing and expanding the network of pipelines contributed to the ascendance of China as a better partner. Enormous loans to Turkmenistan

and generous investments in the pipeline leading to its mainland prioritized China for the Turkmen dictators. Contrary to the assumption that export diversification leads to economic growth and, consequently, development as a whole, it didn't take place in Turkmenistan. Iran has always been constrained by the Western sanctions and limited sources for investment. But China is interested in getting access to the Iranian market and its ports, and the fastest land route lies through Turkmenistan. There have already been test-runs of the trade route and it has a huge potential in contributing to the development of Turkmenistan and Central Asia as a whole. In 2016, the freight train from China to Tehran arrived in 14 days via Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, it usually takes 45 days by sea – unquestionable advantage in speed and avoidance of traditional chokepoints in the sea.⁷⁸ However, engagement in trade means opening the country and exposing the people to the rest of the world. This is certainly a risk to the dictatorial regime of Berdimuhamedov family. Therefore, the rule in Turkmenistan could become an obstacle for the regional integration. Turkey has attempted mixing soft-power tactics and geopolitics, but the local corrupt dictator exterminates any possible risks and threats to his power. Closure of Turkmen-Turkish high schools demonstrate that even ethnic links do not influence the dictators with Soviet mentality. It leads to a pessimistic conclusion that geopolitics negatively impact development in a resource rich developing country. The power that emerges in such circumstances is authoritarian, and it spoils any possible positive aspects of geopolitics by corruption and patronage. Resource curse is more a rule than an exception in Turkmenistan.

3.4 Bad governance in Kyrgyzstan

It is hard to build a practical development strategy in a small poor country because the government lacks sufficient capacity and capability, and the results of the strategy do not come instantly. The most optimistic achievement of good governance can't top more than 10% in economic growth (Collier, 2007, p. 64). Therefore, society often blames the government for slow progress and stagnation. Not only lack of sources but also the shortage of educated people for reforms inhibits development. Another problem with development is that the progress momentum should be sustained. International organizations pressed on former-Soviet creditor countries to meet certain conditions in return for further aid. In Kyrgyzstan it later started being negatively interpreted as the Western interference due to increasing external debt and no significant progress, such perception only helped the Kremlin to regain geopolitical authority. Analyzing post-independence history of

⁷⁸ Bozorgmehr, Najmeh (May 9, 2016): First freight trains from China arrive in Tehran. Financial Times, <https://www.ft.com/content/e964a78e-0bd8-11e6-9456-444ab5211a2f>, retrieved March 15, 2023.

Kyrgyzstan, it is disappointing to note that the country started as the flagman of political and economic liberalization in the post-Soviet Central Asia but has ended in reinstating authoritarian regime recently.

While Central Asia is not friendly for democracy, there is still a good prospect for governance. In order to continue the analysis, the distinction between democracy and good governance in the CA context should be clearly defined. Currently, most of the Central Asian society doesn't demand for more political parties, fair elections or independent parliament per se. Their main concern is that the objective of the government should be to provide social goods and services, improve quality of living and preserve stability. In other words, democracy is a politically inclined ideology, and good governance is a technocratic notion related to effective state management. Young generation of CA is more assertively demanding good governance rather than democracy.⁷⁹ So, if the prospects of democracy are dim in CA, the prospects of development through application of good governance practices are still on the board. Chinese model of top-down development is more comprehensible for Central Asian mentality than democracy-centered bottom-up Western model that is seen as a chaotic mechanism with no means of control. Good governance and democracy are interrelated but they can exist independently from each other as well. Obviously, the best scenario is when both of them are established in the state system.

Fergana valley has a complex structure of borders, enclaves, water and land regulations in addition to its dense population consisting of mainly Uzbeks, Kyrgyz and Tajiks. Ethnic tensions were suppressed or neglected during Soviet Era, but now three countries have to find ways to coexist. The population of southern Kyrgyzstan around Fergana valley is ethnically intermixed with a significant Uzbek minority. With rising social hardship, grievances among Kyrgyz grew, and ethnic clashes erupted in 1990, which resulted in more than 300 casualties, these clashes only intensified Uzbeks' desire for autonomy to eventually unite with Uzbekistan (Hiro, 2011, pp. 275-276). This instability played a fateful role in the origins of democratic principles in Kyrgyzstan. The communists approved establishment of the post of president but objected the appointment of the incumbent first secretary as the first president stating that he couldn't manage the ethnic clashes in the south (Engvall, 2022, p. 19). However, they couldn't agree on who should be the president. Among the new

⁷⁹ Stronski, Paul – Zanca, Russell (October 18, 2019): Societal Change Afoot in Central Asia. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, <https://carnegieendowment.org/2019/10/18/societal-change-afout-in-central-asia-pub-80086>, retrieved March 15, 2023.

candidates, Askar Akaev – physics and math scientist – became the first president and the only leader in CA not closely affiliated with the communists.

Initially, Kyrgyzstan was the champion of democratization and scored high in good governance (Figure 9). Such an early progress was praised and supported by the West. The volume of aid (Figure 4) and assistance in terms of loans rose sharply. In order to ensure further flow of financial assistance, Akaev needed to comply with ‘persuasive’ requests of the Clinton administration and conduct fair presidential elections in 1995 (Hiro, 2011, pp. 285-286). Although the intentions were good, the West pushed Kyrgyzstan further into indebtedness. Akaev learned how to make money from the Western benevolence at the expense of the state economic development. External debt is not a threat per se for a developed economy but the fragile economy like Kyrgyzstan is not capable of repaying accumulating debt when it reaches unsustainable levels. Therefore, when the West warns developing countries about the danger of falling into the debt trap in relations with China, it is actually the West that has initially indebted those countries.

Figure 10: GDP and Debt of Kyrgyzstan (current US\$)

Source: own editing, data source: (1) The World Bank (n.d.): External debt stocks, long-term (DOD, current US\$). The World Bank Open Data, <https://pages.eiu.com/rs/753-RIQ-438/images/eiu-democracy-index-2021.pdf>, retrieved on March 16, 2023. (2) The World Bank (n.d.): GDP (current US\$). The World Bank Open Data, <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>, retrieved on March 16, 2023.

The Western push for economic and political liberalization also had positive effects. NATO PfP was signed in 1994 which was not opposed by Moscow at that time. Kyrgyzstan joined WTO first out of the former Soviet republics in 1998 and opened borders for trade. Large scale privatization attracted first foreign investors. The first big investor was from Canada, Cameco mining corporation signed agreement with the Kyrgyz government to set up a joint venture for Kumtor Gold Mine operations in 1993. Kyrgyzstan would receive 70% of profits,

the agreement would create hundreds of jobs (Anderson, 1999, p. 104). Looking at the Figure 10, it becomes clear what Collier described as the limits of positive effect of good governance on economic growth. GDP was shrinking until 1999, despite all the initial effort of the government. Later, partially due to the stagnant economic condition, disillusioned society would demand the nationalization of the gold mine. Current president Sadyr Japarov had been imprisoned in 2013 for protesting against foreign management of the gold mine, and came to power after the Third Revolution in 2020. So, his first mission as a president was nationalization, which he successfully achieved in 2022.⁸⁰ Clearly, this event is an indicator of harmful governance and it is hard to expect that foreign investors from the West will consider Kyrgyzstan as a safe country for investments and business.

The aftermath of the 9/11 attacks opened a new chapter in the US-Kyrgyzstan relations. In October 2001, Akaev offered Bush administration a deal to use part of the Manas International Airport near Bishkek for the military and logistical purposes during the war against the Taliban in Afghanistan with a nominal annual rent of two million US\$; the offer was accepted and the first American planes arrived in December (Hiro, 2011, p. 290). As early as 2003 plane fuel contracts for US base were in the hands of two mysterious local companies: one affiliated with the son of Akaev and another with his son-in-law. Millions of US\$ had been embezzled through these contracts up until 2005 when Akaev was ousted in the Tulip Revolution. Second president – Kurmanbek Bakiev – unsurprisingly continued exploiting this corruption scheme via a new company affiliated to his son up until he, too, was ousted in the 2010 Revolution. The US Department of Defense refused to share information related to how the company related to Bakiev's son managed to win the tender for fuel contracts (Cooley, 2012, p. 144). At the conference in Moscow in 2009, Bakiev revealed his decision to close the US base and the Russian president Dmitri Medvedev announced assistance of 150US\$ million in grant, 300US\$ million in loans and investment of 1,7US\$ in the hydropower plant (Ibid, p. 124). Inspired by its geopolitical success, Russia also offered to write off 193US\$ million of debt for a 48% stake in the Dastan state enterprise producing torpedoes (Stobdan, 2014, p. 111). In his pursuit of extracting money from both geopolitical powers, Bakiev was bringing his rule closer to its end. The US base was closed during Almazbek Atambayev presidency in 2014; during this period, Kyrgyzstan was the only country in the world to host both US and Russian military bases (Engvall, 2022, p. 82).

⁸⁰ Rickleton, Chris (February 13, 2023): Kyrgyzstan's Kumtor Gold Mine and The Fall of A 'Great Nomad'. Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty, <https://www.rferl.org/a/kyrgyzstan-kumtor-gold-mine-great-nomad/32269064.html>, retrieved March 17, 2023.

Russian geopolitical influence in Kyrgyzstan is very strong. Kyrgyzstan is a member of the CSTO, CIS and EEU, hosts a Russian military base and supplies more than million working migrants to Russia. But the functionality and practicality of these agreements and organizations have been challenged. The 2010 Revolution expanded into ethnic clashes in the south, and interim president – Roza Otunbaeva pleaded for CSTO peacekeeping intervention which was declined (Stobdan, 2014, p. 26). CSTO once again demonstrated its implicit aim as the geopolitical tool of Russia. EEU, which Kyrgyzstan joined in 2015, has been very influential with mixed effect on development. On the one hand, the flow of remittances (Figure 2) increased in 2016 sharply due to a simplified procedure of entrance and work in Russia; on the other hand, re-export of goods from China has declined, which will lead to rise of unemployment (Canaltay, 2016). Despite Russian backwardness, it has often been a model for Kyrgyzstan as a sustainable alternative to democracy. The legislation on foreign agents, adopted by Russia in 2012, might have a twin in Kyrgyzstan because the society sympathizes Moscow’s interpretation of the Western influence through supporting NGOs as a threat to statehood, security and stability.⁸¹ Alexander Cooley (2012, p. 51) suggests that Russian desire to assert itself in Central Asia is intimately related to its great power identity building. Russian Neo-Eurasian geopolitical aspirations are detrimental and incoherent with the development of Kyrgyzstan and Central Asia as a whole.

Trade and aid are Central in the relationship between China and Kyrgyzstan. The WTO accession in 1998 helped Kyrgyzstan to build intensive trade relations despite challenging geography. Tian-Shang mountains separate two states and technically it is cheaper to transport goods through the Kazakh plains, but Kazakhstan was more concentrated in its vast gas and oil resources. As a result, Kyrgyzstan could develop its re-export sector and approximately 75% of import from China used to be re-exported to Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan in the mid-2000 (Peyrouse, 2007, p. 17). Re-export sector still provides jobs to thousands of people, however, shortly after accession to the Russian-led EEU in 2015, the export has started declining. A fundamental BRI project is China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway; the agreement on feasibility studies has been signed between three states during the SCO summit in Samarkand in 2022.⁸² The project is expensive and there are doubts that

⁸¹ Imanaliyeva, Ayzirek (November 10, 2022): Kyrgyzstan: Draft bill promises more pain for ailing NGOs. Eurasianet, <https://eurasianet.org/kyrgyzstan-draft-bill-promises-more-pain-for-ailing-ngos>, retrieved March 19, 2023.

⁸² Imamova, Novbahor (October 4, 2022): Despite Skepticism, China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan Railway Deal Chugs Forward. Voice of America, <https://www.voanews.com/a/despite-skepticism-china-kyrgyzstan-uzbekistan-railway-deal-chugs-forward/6775799.html>, retrieved March 19, 2023.

Kyrgyzstan can finance its portion of the railway construction. Chinese dream to rebuild the Silk Road is expected to have a positive spillover effect on Kyrgyzstan, but it needs to maintain stability and demonstrate good state governance.

Sub-chapter conclusion

Kyrgyzstan as any other Central Asian state has bad governance and a lot of external geopolitical influence. The early post-independence period, though, has started very optimistically with a government inclined towards democracy and hope that with good state management it could develop. The West had used its most common geopolitical tool – aid and assistance which initially generated impetus and motivation for the government to launch reforms. Besides, investors from the West launched the biggest corporation that significantly contributed to the national economy (Stobdan, 2014, pp. 61-62). Traditionally for CA, external aid and FDI have become a source of embezzlement and corruption. The 1995 presidential elections were rigged by Akaev in order ensure further flow aid. Kyrgyzstan has become heavily indebted to WB and IMF. The US military base started as a sign of prospective cooperation with the West, but also ended being overwhelmed with corruption scandals over fuel contracts. Accumulating external debt and military presence of the US frustrated the society and intensified its anti-Western sentiments.

Russia grabbed this opportunity for its geopolitical comeback by stimulating the Second revolution and overthrow of the second president in 2010. Russia has sole control over its CSTO and EEU umbrella organizations. The membership boosted inflow of remittances but damaged the re-export sector, so it is a challenging task to weigh costs and benefits of the Russian influence. The war in Ukraine has intensified the friction between pro-Western and pro-Russian forces within society, and the Russian supporters gain critical ground, but the resent protests in Georgia against anti-Western legislation on NGOs gives hope that Russian toxic influence can be minimized.

Chinese BRI project is destined to reshape CA and integrate its five states. Landlocked, sparsely populated region with old infrastructure and transport routes seriously needs integration and modernization. The BRI promotes unimpeded trade and facilities connectivity that mountainous Kyrgyzstan vitally needs but can't afford. By pursuing its own global geopolitical ambitions, China can actually stimulate development in Kyrgyzstan primarily through its BRI and secondarily through SCO.

4 THESIS CONCLUSION

An analysis of the impact of geopolitics on development cannot lead to a unanimous conclusion. Four regional powers, international organizations and the West engage in the geopolitical game in Central Asia, and each has succeeded to a different degree. In many cases, external actors couldn't achieve their objectives, which suggests that there are other variables that should be taken into account. This study has revealed that local political culture such as resilience to democratization, predisposition towards authoritarianism, characters of the leaders, corrupt behavior and geography significantly define the outcome of a geopolitical involvement. Despite global hegemony of the West, the regional powers are often more successful in Central Asia.

In the case of Tajikistan, the civil war was ended with the efforts of all external actors, however, the state has failed to develop further. Stagnant development still exposes dangers of Tajikistan falling back into another violent conflict. Sporadic clashes between Dushanbe and insurgent forces in GBAO take place to these days, and these conflicts are largely ignored by the international community. Regional powers are interested in keeping the authoritarian regime of Rahmon family in power at the expense of democracy and political rights of the Pamiri people. Rahmon's loyalty to Moscow allows Russia to support current status quo by keeping troops in Tajikistan. Chinese anti-terrorism stance in Central Asia implicitly approves Dushanbe's military forays in GBAO and even provides military assistance through CSO agreements. Iran and Tajikistan have united their efforts for resistance to the Taliban forces in Afghanistan. The US assistance is completely in the interests of Rahmon since the anti-Taliban position of the Washington and Dushanbe's struggles with Afghan Tajik opposition coincide in terms of regional security. The US has been providing military trainings and drills to Tajikistan annually since 2004.⁸³ Dushanbe has been using this assistance and knowledge against the Pamiri people, Afghan Tajiks and neighboring Kyrgyzstan. Geopolitics has been negatively impacting development in Tajikistan because Rahmon has been using external powers' resources and support at his own discretion. *Geopolitics has sponsored dictatorship in Tajikistan and continues to do so as Rahmon prepares to transfer power to his son.*

Geopolitics in doubly-landlocked Uzbekistan has played a crucial role in development. Unique geography of Uzbekistan, according to Collier, has made it very dependent on its

⁸³ U.S. Embassy Dushanbe (August 10, 2022): REGIONAL COOPERATION 2022 Military Exercise Begins in Dushanbe. U.S. Embassy in Tajikistan, <https://tj.usembassy.gov/regional-cooperation-22/>, retrieved March 19, 2023.

neighbors for development. Connectivity and regional integration are especially important. However, besides or even despite its geography, Uzbekistan is a powerful state capable of exerting its influence on its neighbors. The US had cooperated with Tashkent and practically accepted Karimov's authoritarian personality, which was interpreted as a *carte blanche* by Karimov for building one of the most repressive regimes. Washington even secretly collaborated in identifying and transporting opposition figures in the hands of Karimov security services. EBRD's straightforward criticism against human rights violations deteriorated relations with the West, and Uzbekistan evicted the K2 US military base in 2005 after Andijan protests. In order to cooperate with China, Uzbekistan first had to build friendly relations with Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. Chinese no interference and business-only approach allowed it to build a gas pipeline from Turkmenistan to its mainland through Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. The railway to Iran follows the same route. Another railway from China via Kyrgyzstan is under feasibility studies. But the biggest progress in development was possible only after Karimov's death in 2016, when a bit more liberal Mirziyoyev managed to ease the tension. This development progress is not an outcome of only geopolitics. *The impact of geopolitics on development in the case of Uzbekistan has again proved that the outcome significantly depends on the characteristics of the local politicians in power.*

Turkmenistan, unlike Uzbekistan, has wasted its geopolitical advantages and couldn't reach sustainable development either. The main reason of such a failure is megalomaniac personality of its leaders and their corruptness. Enormous gas reserves could serve as a source for current consumption, economic growth and investments in the future, however, the revenues ended up offshore in the bank accounts of Deutsche Bank. Before and after Turkmenistan's official neutrality in 1995, the US showed masterclass of secretly cooperating with a totalitarian regime and tolerance. Russian scramble for the Turkmen gas showed Putin's ability to compromise the fate of ethnic Russian people in Turkmenistan. The war in Ukraine, on the other hand, has shown that Putin can emphasize ethnic Russian people abroad thesis as the cornerstone of Moscow's foreign policy and geopolitics. Iran's geopolitical incursions have not been pernicious but beneficial for development. Tehran's concern is to earn on transit of Turkmen gas and examine feasibility of developing trade routes with China via Turkmenistan. Turkey pursues similar geopolitical goals but also considers utilizing trans-Caspian energy and trade routes in order to pass around Iran and Russia. The most successful power in Turkmenistan is China with its trans-Central Asian gas pipeline. On the one hand, this pipeline technically diversifies Ashgabat's gas exports,

on the other hand, it doesn't impact development since the dictator comfortably keeps power and extracts revenues for personal enrichment. *The impact of geopolitics on development in Turkmenistan has been extremely negative since tolerance and neglect of the schizophrenic Turkmen dictators only strengthened their power.*

Geopolitical activity has been the most intensive in Kyrgyzstan despite its 'regionally average' geography and lack of substantial natural resources. The post-independence path of Kyrgyzstan has started very differently from the rest of CA. A non-communist Akaev becomes the first president and, on such an optimistic note, close cooperation with the West started in the early 1990's. The Western assistance started flowing in the country which, interestingly, generated hazardous dependency on external sources. This can also be interpreted as a type of Dutch disease (Collier, 2007, pp. 162-163). Akaev started showing worrying signs of governance deterioration in order to ensure inflow of assistance. Kyrgyzstan started drowning in debt. But it should be noted that early democratization process has nurtured pro-Western layer in the civil society which is very active even to these days. Russia certainly could see Kyrgyzstan drifting away from its sphere of influence. Moscow activated pro-Russian layer of Kyrgyz society and manipulated political leaders with mainly financial assistance. Russia had no intentions or capacity to develop Kyrgyzstan. The role of Bishkek in the geopolitical map of Moscow was similar to Dushanbe's loyal subordination. Early trade relations with China have actually had positive impact on nurturing a middle-class layer engaged in re-export sector. Now Chinese objective is to expand trade and connectivity of CA as a whole. Railway to Uzbekistan through Kyrgyzstan needs stability in the region to function properly. China needs a stable and integrated region for its New Silk Road dream, more known as BRI. *Currently, it is hard to measure the impact of geopolitics on development in Kyrgyzstan. However, Kyrgyzstan is a perfect example of how even a moderately liberal leadership can capitalize on geopolitical activity and generate positive impetus for development.*

5 References

- Aga Khan Development Network. (n.d.). *Frequently Asked Questions*. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from Aga Khan Development Network official website: <https://the.akdn/en/how-we-work/our-approach/frequently-asked-questions>
- Akinchenko, M. (Producer), & Tolstoy, P. (Director). (2019). *Za proshedshie pjat' let fraza «pechen'ki Nuland» stala ne menee ustojchivoj, chem «30 srebrenikov»* [Motion Picture]. Retrieved March 11, 2023, from https://www.1tv.ru/news/2019-04-21/363944-za_proshedshie_pyat_let_fraza_pechenki_Nuland_stala_ne_menee_ustoychivoy_chem_30_srebrenikov
- Aliasgariy, S., & Ekstrom, M. (2021, October 21). *Chabahar Port and Iran's Strategic Balancing With China and India*. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from The Diplomat: <https://thediplomat.com/2021/10/chabahar-port-and-irans-strategic-balancing-with-china-and-india/>
- Anderson, J. (1999). *Kyrgyzstan: Central Asia's island of democracy?* Australia: Harwood Academic Publishers.
- Arynova, A., & Schmeier, S. (2021, August 1). *Conflicts over water and water infrastructure at the Tajik-Kyrgyz border [Electronic copy]*. Retrieved February 23, 2023, from Water, Peace and Security: <https://waterpeacesecurity.org/files/68>
- Aslund, A. (2007). *How capitalism was built: the transformation of Central and Eastern Europe, Russia and Central Asia*. Cambridge, New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Barnes, C., & Abdullaev, K. (2001, April). From war to politics. (C. Barnes, & K. Abdullaev, Eds.) *Accord: Politics of Compromise: The Tajikistan Peace Process*(10), 8-14. Retrieved February 25, 2023, from <https://www.c-r.org/accord/tajikistan/key-elements-tajikistan-peace-agreement>
- Baunov, P. (2022, June 20). *Face to face with Putin, Kazakhstan's president refuses to recognise Ukraine breakaway republics*. Retrieved March 10, 2023, from bne IntelliNews: <https://intellinews.com/face-to-face-with-putin-kazakhstan-s-president-refuses-to-recognise-ukraine-breakaway-republics-248002/>
- Blouet, B. W. (2005). Halford Mackinder and the Pivotal Heartland. In B. W. Blouet (Ed.), *Global geostrategy: Mackinder and the defence of the West* (pp. 1-16). New York: Taylor & Francis Group.
- Bohr, A. (2016). *Turkmenistan: Power, Politics and Petro-Authoritarianism*. London: Chatham House.
- Bozorgmehr, N. (2016, May 9). *First freight trains from China arrive in Tehran*. Retrieved March 15, 2023, from Financial Times: <https://www.ft.com/content/e964a78e-0bd8-11e6-9456-444ab5211a2f>
- BP p.l.c. (2022). *bp Statistical Review of World Energy 2022*. London: BP p.l.c. Retrieved March 15, 2023, from <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2022-full-report.pdf>
- Brenton, C. (2022, April 10). *Persian games: Iran's strategic foothold in Tajikistan*. Retrieved January 2, 2023, from openDemocracy: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/odr/persian-games-irans-strategic-foothold-in-tajikistan/>
- Burna-Asefi, S. (2023, February 27). *Just Passing Through: Kazakhstan's Parallel Trade Predicament*. Retrieved March 3, 2023, from The Diplomat: <https://thediplomat.com/2023/02/just-passing-through-kazakhstans-parallel-trade-predicament/>
- Canaltay, C. (2016, March). Kyrgyzstan in Eurasian Economic Union: Benefits and Losses. (A. Amirbek, Ed.) *Asya Avrupa*(3), pp. 26-32. Retrieved March 18, 2023, from <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/asya-avrupa-no-3/>

- Chowdhury, A., & Erdenebileg, S. (2006). *Geography Against Development: A Case for Landlocked Developing Countries*. New York: United Nations.
- Cohen, R. S. (2020, December 30). *Why We 'Send Them Money'*. Retrieved February 12, 2023, from The RAND Corporation: <https://www.rand.org/blog/2020/12/why-we-send-them-money.html>
- Collective Security Treaty Organization. (n.d.). *From the Treaty to the Organization*. Retrieved January 23, 2023, from Collective Security Treaty Organization: <https://en.odkb-csto.org/25years/>
- Collier, P. (2007). *The Bottom Billion: Why the Poorest Countries are failing and what can be done about it*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Committee for the Abolition of Illegitimate Debt. (2007, January 30). *Kyrgyz Protesters Target World Bank Debt Scheme*. Retrieved February 18, 2023, from Committee for the Abolition of Illegitimate Debt: <https://www.cadtm.org/Kyrgyz-Protesters-Target-World>
- Cooley, A. (2012). *Great Games, Local Rules: The New Great Power Contest in Central Asia*. New York, New York, USA: Oxford University Press.
- Daniyarova, A. (2022, November 11). *Organization of Turkic States meets in Uzbekistan*. Retrieved March 7, 2023, from Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies: <https://www.ankasam.org/organization-of-turkic-states-meets-in-uzbekistan/?lang=en>
- Diakonoff, I. (1999). *The Paths of History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Dickens, M. (1989). The impact of Russo-Soviet culture in Central Asia. Retrieved October 9, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/398259/The_Impact_of_Russo_Soviet_Culture_In_Central_Asia?email_work_card=reading-history
- Donnellon-May, G. (2022, October 13). *Turkey's Growing Influence in Central Asia*. Retrieved October 15, 2022, from The Diplomat: <https://thediplomat.com/2022/10/turkeys-growing-influence-in-central-asia/>
- Doolotkeldieva, A., & Marat, E. (2022, October 4). *Why Russia and China Aren't Intervening in Central Asia*. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from Foreign Policy Magazine: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2022/10/04/tajikistan-kyrgyzstan-russia-china-intervention-central-asia/>
- Dugin, A. (2014). *Eurasian Mission: An Introduction to New-Eurasianism*. London: Arktos Media Ltd.
- Economist Intelligence Unit. (2022). *Democracy Index 2021: The China Challenge*. Retrieved December 23, 2022, from Economist Intelligence Unit: <https://pages.eiu.com/rs/753-RIQ-438/images/eiu-democracy-index-2021.pdf>
- Engvall, J. (2022). *Between Bandits and Bureaucrats: 30 Years of Parliamentary Development in Kyrgyzstan*. Washington D.C., Stockholm: Central Asia-Caucasus Institute and Silk Road Studies Program.
- Eurasianet. (2016, July 26). *Kyrgyzstan: Antagonism Grows with Turkey Over Gülen Links*. Retrieved January 29, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/kyrgyzstan-antagonism-grows-turkey-over-gulen-links>
- Eurasianet. (2022, July 28). *Tajikistan puts the squeeze on Aga Khan-linked entities*. Retrieved January 29, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/tajikistan-puts-the-squeeze-on-aga-khan-linked-entities>
- Eurasianet. (2022, October 17). *Was Tajik leader's rant at Putin defiance or a plea for greater dependence?* Retrieved January 1, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/was-tajik-leaders-rant-at-putin-defiance-or-a-plea-for-greater-dependence>
- Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. (n.d.). *Our Mission*. Retrieved March 1, 2023, from EITI: <https://eiti.org/our-mission>
- Feneis, R. (1992). *Pan-Turkism, Turkey, and the Muslim Peoples of the Former Soviet Union: A Modern Problem in Historical Context*. U.S. Army War College. Carlisle: U.S. Army War College. Retrieved from <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA251827>

- Fitzpatrick, C. A. (2011, August 22). *Turkmenistan: Turkish Schools Closed Amid Concerns of Spread of Nurchilar Movement*. Retrieved March 13, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/turkmenistan-turkish-schools-closed-amid-concerns-of-spread-of-nurchilar-movement>
- Foltz, R. (2019). *A history of the Tajiks: Iranians of the East*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc.
- Geographic Guide. (n.d.). *Map of Central Asia - 2005*. Retrieved February 2, 2023, from Geographic Guide: <https://www.geographicguide.com/asia/maps/central-asia.htm>
- GlobalSecurity.org. (n.d.). *Operational Group of Russian Forces in Tajikistan*. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from GlobalSecurity.org: <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/russia/ogrv-tajikistan.htm>
- Gökhun Dayıoğlu, A. (2022, June). Hungarian Nationalism and Hungarian Pan-Turanism until the Beginning of the Second World War. *Politics in Central Europe*, 18(2), 225-249. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2478/pce-2022-0010>
- Golden, P. B. (2011). *Central Asia in World History*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Goryayev, V. (2001). Architecture of international involvement in the Tajik peace process. (C. Barnes, & K. Abdullaev, Eds.) *Accord: Politics of Compromise: The Tajikistan Peace Process*(10), 32-37. Retrieved February 25, 2023, from <https://www.c-r.org/accord/tajikistan/key-elements-tajikistan-peace-agreement>
- Grogan, L. (2021). *Civil War, Famine and the Persistence of Human Capital: Evidence from Tajikistan*. Bonn: IZA – Institute of Labor Economics. Retrieved February 10, 2023, from <https://docs.iza.org/dp14775.pdf>
- Grygiel, J., & Mitchell, W. (2016). *The Unquiet Frontier: Rising Rivals, Vulnerable Allies, and the Crisis of American Power*. Princeton, New Jersey, USA: Princeton University Press.
- Guarascio, F., & Pirnazarov, N. (2022, July 6). *EU plans investment in world's tallest dam to dent Russia's energy clout*. Retrieved March 17, 2023, from Reuters: <https://www.reuters.com/article/ukraine-crisis-eu-tajikistan-idAFL8N2YM2FR>
- Hedlund, S. (2022, August 24). *Uzbekistan's bumpy ride out of Russia's orbit*. Retrieved March 7, 2023, from Geopolitical Intelligence Services: <https://www.gisreportsonline.com/r/uzbekistan-russia-relations/>
- Hiro, D. (2011). *Inside Central Asia*. London: Duckworth Overlook.
- Hopkirk, P. (1990). *The Great Game: On Secret Service in High Asia*. London: John Murray Publishers.
- Human Development Report Office. (n.d.). *Human Development Index (HDI)*. Retrieved March 18, 2023, from HDI UNDP: <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>
- Human Development Reports. (n.d.). *What is Human Development?* Retrieved February 2, 2023, from Human Development Reports of United Nations Development Programme: <https://hdr.undp.org/about/human-development>
- Human Rights Watch. (2020, September 23). *Turkmenistan: Denial, Inaction Worsen Food Crisis*. Retrieved March 18, 2023, from Human Rights Watch: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/09/23/turkmenistan-denial-inaction-worsen-food-crisis>
- Huntington, S. P. (1996). *The Clash of Civilizations and The Remaking of World Order* (August 2011 ed.). New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Hussein, M., & Haddad, M. (2021, September 10). *Infographic: US military presence around the world*. Retrieved October 25, 2022, from Al Jazeera: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/10/infographic-us-military-presence-around-the-world-interactive>
- Imamova, N. (2022a, November 11). *Uzbekistan Asked to Allow Foreign Experts to Investigate Unrest in Karakalpakstan*. Retrieved February 18, 2023, from Voice of America: <https://www.voanews.com/a/uzbekistan-asked-to-allow-foreign-experts-to-investigate-unrest-in-karakalpakstan/6829826.html>

- Imamova, N. (2022b, October 4). *Despite Skepticism, China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan Railway Deal Chugs Forward*. Retrieved March 19, 2023, from Voice of America: <https://www.voanews.com/a/despite-skepticism-china-kyrgyzstan-uzbekistan-railway-deal-chugs-forward/6775799.html>
- Imanaliyeva, A. (2022, November 10). *Kyrgyzstan: Draft bill promises more pain for ailing NGOs*. Retrieved March 19, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/kyrgyzstan-draft-bill-promises-more-pain-for-ailing-ngos>
- IMF. (2021, February 22). *IMF Conditionality*. Retrieved February 13, 2023, from International Monetary Fund: <https://www.imf.org/en/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2016/08/02/21/28/IMF-Conditionality>
- IMF. (2023, February 13). *IMF Members' Quotas and Voting Power, and IMF Board of Governors*. Retrieved February 13, 2023, from IMF: <https://www.imf.org/en/About/executive-board/members-quotas#U>
- Indeo, F. (2020, December 22). *Turkmenistan's neutrality: rising security problems*. Retrieved March 12, 2023, from NATO Defense College Foundation: <https://www.natofoundation.org/central-asia/turkmenistans-neutrality-rising-security-problems/>
- Institute for Economics and Peace. (2022). *Global Peace Index 2021*. Retrieved December 23, 2022, from Vision of Humanity: <https://www.visionofhumanity.org/maps/#/>
- Jacoby, V. (2017). *If Only It Was Only Water... The Strained Relationship between Tajikistan and Uzbekistan* (2013). In M. Laruelle (Ed.), *Uzbekistan: Political Order, Societal Changes, and Cultural Transformations* (pp. 123-127). Washington D.C.: Central Asia Program.
- Janik, S. (2020, November 12). *The Shanghai Cooperation Organization: A Testbed for Chinese Power Projection*. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from US-China Economic and Security Review Commission: <https://www.uscc.gov/research/shanghai-cooperation-organization-testbed-chinese-power-projection>
- Johnson, D. (2017, December 14). *ZAPAD 2017 and Euro-Atlantic security*. Retrieved November 3, 2022, from NATO official website: <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/articles/2017/12/14/zapad-2017-and-euro-atlantic-security/index.html>
- Kaleji, V. (2022, June 14). *Iran Opens Ababil-2 Drone Factory in Tajikistan: Reasons and Implications*. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from The Jamestown Foundation: Eurasia Daily Monitor: <https://jamestown.org/program/iran-opens-ababil-2-drone-factory-in-tajikistan-reasons-and-implications/>
- Kanapiyanova, Z. (n.d.). *Turkmenistan-Russia Energy Cooperation in the Context of Natural Gas Trading*. Retrieved March 12, 2023, from Eurasian Research Institute: <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/turkmenistan-russia-energy-cooperation-in-the-context-of-natural-gas-trading/>
- Kaplan, R. D. (2018). *The Return of Marco Polo's World: War, Strategy and American Interests in the Twenty-first Century*. New York: Random House.
- Karpazli, E. (2016, June 25). *Kyrgyzstan still burying the past 100 years after Urkun*. Retrieved November 23, 2022, from TRT World: <https://www.trtworld.com/magazine/kyrgyzstan-still-burying-the-past-100-years-after-urkun-1833>
- Kaufmann, D., & Kraay, A. (n.d.). *Worldwide Governance Indicators*. Retrieved March 12, 2023, from Worldwide Governance Indicators: <http://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/>
- Khanna, P. (2008). *The Second World: Empires and the Influence in the New World Order*. New York: Random House.
- Kizilay, S. (2022, December 2). *Tajikistan-China Military Cooperation*. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from Ankara Center for Crisis and Policy Studies: <https://www.ankasam.org/tajikistan-china-military-cooperation/?lang=en>
- Kostem, S. (2019, October 1). *The Power of the Quiet? Turkey's Central Asia Strategy*. Retrieved January 30, 2023, from Italian Institute for International Political Studies:

- <https://www.ispionline.it/en/publication/power-quiet-turkeys-central-asia-strategy-24069>
- Kovalev, P. (2022, October 13). *Uchenija ODKB v Kirgizii perenesli na bolee pozdnij srok*. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from TASS: <https://tass.ru/mezhdunarodnaya-panorama/16044133>
- Kucera, J. (2022, January 5). *CSTO agrees to intervene in Kazakhstan unrest*. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/csto-agrees-to-intervene-in-kazakhstan-unrest>
- Lachert, J. (2019, 03 14). *Post-Soviet frozen conflicts: a challenge for european security*. Retrieved 11 20, 2021, from Warsaw Institute: <https://warsawinstitute.org/post-soviet-frozen-conflicts-challenge-european-security/>
- Lipman, M. (2015, March 13). *How Russia has come to loathe the West*. Retrieved March 10, 2023, from European Council on Foreign Relations: https://ecfr.eu/article/commentary_how_russia_has_come_to_loathe_the_west311346/
- Machalek, K. (n.d.). *Factsheet: Russia's NGO Laws*. Retrieved March 11, 2023, from Freedom House: https://freedomhouse.org/sites/default/files/Fact%20Sheet_0.pdf
- Mejlumyan, A. (2022, September 15). *For Armenians, CSTO missing in action*. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/for-armenians-csto-missing-in-action>
- Meteojurnal. (2021, May 27). *Istorija formirovanija granicy Turkmenskoj SSR*. Retrieved January 14, 2023, from Metejournal: <https://metejournal.ru/istoriya-formirovaniya-granicy-turkmenskoj-ssr/>
- Miller, T. (2017). *China's Asian Dream: Empire Building along the New Silk Road*. London: Zed Books Ltd.
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Türkiye. (n.d.). *Türkiye's Multilateral Transportation Policy*. Retrieved January 30, 2023, from Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Türkiye official website: https://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkey_s-multilateral-transportation-policy.en.mfa
- Motyl, V. (Director). (1970). *White Sun of the Desert* [Motion Picture].
- Muratbekova, A. (n.d.). *2022 SCO Summit in Samarkand: Key Takeaways*. Retrieved March 7, 2023, from Eurasian Research Institute: <https://www.eurasian-research.org/publication/2022-sco-summit-in-samarkand-key-takeaways/>
- Najibullah, F. (2022, March 26). *Central Asian Migrants Losing Work As Russian Businesses Downsize Or Close*. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty: <https://www.rferl.org/a/russia-sanctions-central-asian-migrants/31771858.html>
- OECD. (2003, April 22). Papers on Official Development Assistance (ODA). *The DAC Journal*, 3(4), III-3 - III-35. doi:https://doi.org/10.1787/journal_dev-v3-art27-en
- Organization of Turkic States. (n.d.). *Areas of Cooperation*. Retrieved January 29, 2023, from Organization of Turkic States: <https://www.turkicstates.org/en/isbirligi-alanlari>
- OSCE Forum for Security Co-operation. (2011, November 30). *Vienna Document 2011 on Confidence- and Security-building measures*. Retrieved February 13, 2023, from Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe: <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/4/86597.pdf>
- Overy, R. (2020, December 4). *In search of Lebensraum*. Retrieved November 18, 2022, from Engelsberg Ideas: <https://engelsbergideas.com/essays/in-search-of-lebensraum/>
- Pannier, B. (2022, September 13). *Europe's Wait for Turkmen Natural Gas Continues*. Retrieved March 13, 2023, from Foreign Policy Research Institute: <https://www.fpri.org/article/2022/09/europes-wait-for-turkmen-natural-gas-continues/>
- Paramonov, V. (2017). China's Economic Presence in Uzbekistan Realities and Potentials (2014). In M. Laruelle (Ed.), *Uzbekistan: Political Order, Societal Changes, and Cultural Transformations* (pp. 149-156). Washington D.C.: Central Asia Program.
- Parshin, P. B. (2016). Mesto i rol' Gorno-Badakhshanskoj avtonomnoj oblasti v gosudarstvennoj sisteme Tadjikistana. *Mezhdunarodnaya Analitika*(2), pp. 83-96. Retrieved from <https://www.interanalytics.org/jour/article/view/10/11>

- Peyrouse, S. (2007). *Economic Aspects of the Chinese-Central Asia Rapprochement*. Washington, D.C., Stockholm: Central Asia-Caucasus Institute and Silk Road Studies Program.
- Reynolds, A. N. (2021, August 3). *Opinion: Kazakhstan's oil sector is rife with human rights abuses*. Retrieved February 16, 2023, from The Third Pole: <https://www.thethirdpole.net/en/energy/kazakhstans-oil-sector-is-rife-with-human-rights-abuses/>
- RFERL Tajik Service. (2022, June 22). *Fear And Outrage In Pamir: Tajikistan's Gorno-Badakhshan Reeling From Brutal State Crackdown*. Retrieved March 2, 2023, from Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty: <https://www.rferl.org/a/tajikistan-gorno-badakhshan-brutal-crackdown/31910506.html>
- Rickleton, C. (2023, February 13). *Kyrgyzstan's Kumtor Gold Mine And The Fall Of A 'Great Nomad'*. Retrieved March 17, 2023, from Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty: <https://www.rferl.org/a/kyrgyzstan-kumtor-gold-mine-great-nomad/32269064.html>
- Rostow, W. W. (1959). The Stages of Economic Growth. *The Economic History Review*, 12(1), 1-16. Retrieved February 4, 2023, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2591077>
- Russell Mead, W. (2014, May/June). The Return of Geopolitics: The Revenge of the Revisionist Powers. *Foreign Affairs*, 93(3). Retrieved October 31, 2021, from <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/china/2014-04-17/return-geopolitics>
- Russian-Kyrgyz Development Fund. (2022, July 19). *Vydannye kredity na 01.12.2022*. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from Russian-Kyrgyz Development Fund official website: <https://www.rkdf.org/vidannie-kredit/>
- Schulz, D. (2022, March 4). *China-Tajikistan Bilateral Relations*. Retrieved March 2, 2023, from Caspian Policy Center: <https://www.caspianpolicy.org/research/security-and-politics-program-spp/china-tajikistan-bilateral-relations>
- Sen, A. (2000). *Development as Freedom*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf, Inc.
- Sindelar, D., & Toiken, S. (2012, December 16). *A Year After Deadly Riots, Zhanaozen Is Quiet But Angry*. Retrieved March 17, 2023, from Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty: <https://www.rferl.org/a/zhanaozen-a-year-after-the-riots/24798726.html>
- SIPRI. (n.d.). *SIPRI Military Expenditure Database*. Retrieved March 11, 2023, from Stockholm International Peace Research Institute: <https://www.sipri.org/databases/milex>
- Standish, R. (2016b, May 25). *How Tajikistan's President Extended his Term - for Life*. Retrieved March 10, 2023, from Foreign Policy Magazine: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2016/05/25/how-tajikistans-president-extended-his-term-for-life-rahmon-isis-migrant-imf/>
- Standish, R. (2021a, October 14). *From A Secret Base in Tajikistan, China's War On Terror Adjusts To A New Reality*. Retrieved December 7, 2022, from Radio Free Europe Radio Liberty: <https://gandhara.rferl.org/a/tajikistan-china-war-on-terror-afghan/31509370.html>
- Stepansky, J. (2021, August 23). *US military presence in Central Asia unlikely amid Taliban rise*. Retrieved November 6, 2022, from Al Jazeera: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/8/23/us-military-presence-in-central-asia-unlikely-amid-taliban-rise>
- Stobdan, P. (2014). *Central Asia: Democracy, Instability and Strategic Game in Kyrgyzstan*. New Delhi: Pentagon Press.
- Stronski, P., & Zanca, R. (2019, October 18). *Societal Change Afoot in Central Asia*. Retrieved March 15, 2023, from Carnegie Endowment for International Peace: <https://carnegieendowment.org/2019/10/18/societal-change-afoot-in-central-asia-pub-80086>
- Stumpf, I. (2009). Rediscovering the State and the Neo-Weberian State. *Annales Universitatis Scientiarum de Rolando Eötvös Nominatae Sectio Iuridica*, 50, 405-418. Retrieved March 29, 2023, from <https://edit.elte.hu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10831/41806/020.pdf>
- Sullivan, C. J. (2019, March 27). *The Superpower and the "Stans": Why Central Asia is Not "Central" to the United States*. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from The SAIS Review of

- International Affairs: <https://saisreview.sais.jhu.edu/the-superpower-and-the-stans-why-central-asia-is-not-central-to-the-united-states/>
- Tastekin, F. (2022, September 26). *Are Turkish drones complicating disputes in Central Asia?* Retrieved January 28, 2023, from Al-Monitor.com: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/09/are-turkish-drones-complicating-disputes-central-asia>
- Tastekin, F. (2023, January 5). *Turkey spars with China over Uyghurs, but is it real?* Retrieved January 29, 2023, from Al-Monitor.com: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2023/01/turkey-spars-china-over-uyghurs-it-real>
- The Economist. (2019, December 21). *Which nation improved the most in 2019?* Retrieved March 7, 2023, from The Economist: <https://www.economist.com/leaders/2019/12/21/which-nation-improved-the-most-in-2019>
- The Kremlin. (2016, September 17). *Wreath laying at memorials in Kyrgyzstan.* Retrieved February 20, 2023, from The Kremlin: <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/52906>
- The Observatory of Economic Complexity. (n.d.). *Turkmenistan.* Retrieved February 16, 2023, from The Observatory of Economic Complexity: <https://oec.world/en/profile/country/tkm>
- The U.S. Central Command. (n.d.). *Command Priorities.* Retrieved November 17, 2022, from The U.S. Central Command official website: <https://www.centcom.mil/ABOUT-US/COMMAND-PRIORITIES/>
- The US Global Leadership Coalition. (2017, February 27). *A letter to Speaker Ryan, Minority Leader Pelosi, Majority Leader McConnell, and Minority Leader Schumer.* Retrieved February 12, 2023, from The US Global Leadership Coalition: https://www.usglc.org/downloads/2017/02/FY18_International_Affairs_Budget_House_Senate.pdf
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *External debt stocks, long-term (DOD, current US\$).* Retrieved March 16, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/DT.DOD.DLXF.CD>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *GDP (current US\$).* Retrieved February 15, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *GDP growth (annual %).* Retrieved February 25, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *Net ODA received (% of GNI).* Retrieved February 11, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/DT.ODA.ODAT.GN.ZS>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *Personal remittances, received (% of GDP).* Retrieved February 11, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.TRF.PWKR.DT.GD.ZS>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). *Total natural resources rents (% of GDP).* Retrieved February 22, 2023, from The World Bank Open Data: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.TOTL.RT.ZS>
- Tian, H. (2018). Chapter 3. China's Conditional Aid and its Impact in Central Asia. In M. Laruelle (Ed.), *China's Belt and Road Initiative and its Impact in Central Asia* (pp. 21-33). Washington, D.C.: Central Asia Program.
- Turkey spars with China over Uyghurs, but is it real?* (2023, January 5). Retrieved January 29, 2023, from Al-Monitor.com: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2023/01/turkey-spars-china-over-uyghurs-it-real>
- Tynan, D. (2010, July 12). *Pentagon Paid Airport Fees to Turkmenistan, But Can't Say How Much.* Retrieved March 12, 2023, from Eurasianet: <https://eurasianet.org/pentagon-paid-airport-fees-to-turkmenistan-but-cant-say-how-much>
- U.S. Embassy Dushanbe. (2022, August 10). *REGIONAL COOPERATION 2022 Military Exercise Begins in Dushanbe.* Retrieved March 19, 2023, from U.S. Embassy in Tajikistan: <https://tj.usembassy.gov/regional-cooperation-22/>
- U.S. Mission Uzbekistan. (2022, October 26). *United States Presents Military Equipment to Uzbekistan's Ministry of Defense.* Retrieved February 18, 2023, from U.S. Embassy in

- Uzbekistan: <https://uz.usembassy.gov/united-states-presents-military-equipment-to-uzbekistans-ministry-of-defense/>
- Umarov, T. (2021, April 6). *Is There a Place for a U.S. Military Base in Central Asia?* Retrieved January 6, 2023, from Carnegie Endowment for International Peace: <https://carnegiemoscow.org/commentary/84685>
- UN News. (2022, October 12). *Ukraine: UN General Assembly demands Russia reverse course on 'attempted illegal annexation'*. Retrieved October 30, 2022, from UN News official website: <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/10/1129492>
- Urciuolo, L. (2022). *Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan: causes and analysis of an endless border dispute [Electronic copy]*. Rome: SpecialEurasia. Retrieved February 23, 2023, from <https://www.specialeurasia.com/2022/09/29/kyrgyzstan-tajikistan-borders/>
- US Department of State Archive. (n.d.). *The Truman Doctrine, 1947*. Retrieved December 29, 2022, from US Department of State Archive: <https://2001-2009.state.gov/r/pa/ho/time/cwr/82210.htm>
- Wallerstein, I. (2006). *European Universalism : the Rhetoric of Power*. New York, London: The New Press.
- Wolczuk, K., Dragneva, R., & Wallace, J. (2022, July 15). *What is the Eurasian Economic Union?* Retrieved January 30, 2023, from Chatham House: <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2022/07/what-eurasian-economic-union>
- World Nuclear Association. (2022). *World Uranium Mining Production*. Retrieved March 31, 2023, from World Nuclear Association: <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/mining-of-uranium/world-uranium-mining-production.aspx>
- Yuldasheva, G. (2017). *The Role of Iran and the United States of America in Geopolitics of Central Asia*. Riga: Latvian Institute of International Affairs. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from https://liia.lv/en/publications/the-role-of-iran-and-the-united-states-of-america-in-geopolitics-of-central-asia-619?get_file=1

Declaration of Originality

Student's Name: Samat Kozhobaev

Neptun code: SSALY0

Title of Thesis: Geopolitics and Development in Central Asia

Hereby, I, a student of the Faculty of Humanities at the University of Pécs, in full knowledge of my liability, declare that this thesis is **my own original work**. I have clearly referenced all sources (both from printed and electronic sources) in the text in accordance with international requirements of copyright.

I acknowledge that it is considered plagiarism

- to cite verbatim without using quotation marks and crediting the author
- to paraphrase the source material without citing the source
- to indicate another author's published ideas as my own.

I declare that I have understood the definition of plagiarism and I accept that if my thesis violates copyrights, its assessment shall be fail (1), and the major director of the program shall initiate a disciplinary procedure in front of the Dean according to Article 59 (14) of the Code of Studies and Examinations of the University of Pécs

I further declare that I will upload my Thesis submitted in accordance with Section 59 (8) of the Code of Studies and Examinations to the electronic system provided by the University (Neptun) by the end of the second week after the submission deadline at the latest.

Pécs, 3rd April, 2023

signed by student

Copyright disclaimer

Name	Samat Kozhobaev
University/Faculty	University of Pécs / Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
Major	International Relations
Full-time/Part-time	Full-time
Year of thesis submission	2023
Title of the thesis	Geopolitics and Development in Central Asia
Name of advisor	Dr. Péter Kacziba
5 keywords for searching	Central Asia, geopolitics, development, landlocked, democracy

I. *

I, the undersigned, author and the sole copyright owner of this thesis hereby grant to make it available to the University of Pécs after electronic submission, without time limit, for purposes of scientific research, to any person designated by the University.

II. *

I, the undersigned, author and the sole copyright owner of this thesis do not consent to my thesis being made available for scientific research purposes at the University of Pécs.

Pécs, 3rd April, 2023

.....
the signature of the student

* – Please mark the preferred section!